

San Beda College Alabang
MASTER IN BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION

**PERCEIVED ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT AND ORGANIZATIONAL
COMMITMENT: A PREDICTIVE STUDY AMONG
PROJECT MANAGERS AT 77GSI**

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That in all things, God may be glorified

ABSTRACT

The Philippine IT consulting sector projects a 22.6% attrition rate (Aon, 2025), raising retention stakes for boundary-spanning project managers susceptible to home-firm disengagement. This *ex post facto* causal study examined whether Perceived Organizational Support (POS) predicts Organizational Commitment (OC) among 75 project managers at Seven Seven Global Services, Inc. (77GSI). POS was measured with the 8-item Survey of Perceived Organizational Support (Eisenberger et al., 1986) and OC with the 18-item Three-Component Model Employee Commitment Survey (Meyer & Allen, 1991). Descriptive results indicated Slightly High levels of POS ($M = 5.26$) and OC, with Normative Commitment ranking highest ($M = 5.02$). Four simple linear regression analyses rejected all null hypotheses: POS significantly predicted Overall OC ($R^2 = .461$), Affective Commitment ($R^2 = .424$), Normative Commitment ($R^2 = .399$), and Continuance Commitment ($R^2 = .090$). The slope for Normative Commitment ($b = 0.780$) exceeded that for Affective Commitment ($b = 0.634$), reversing the affective-dominant pattern typical of Western samples and reflecting the Filipino cultural value of *utang na loob*. Findings inform a proposed Management Development Program at 77GSI grounded in item-level POS analysis.

Keywords: perceived organizational support, organizational commitment, project managers, boundary spanning, IT consulting, Philippines

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That in all things, God may be glorified

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CHAPTER I:

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

Introduction

Modern companies today face a constant struggle to attract and keep the right talent. This challenge is even more visible in the Philippine consulting sector. In a recent report shared by the British-American firm Aon (2025) from their Salary Increase and Turnover Study, it showed that the Philippine's consulting sector has the highest projected attrition rate at 22.6% even surpassing Singapore at 19.3% and Malaysia at 18.2%. For an IT consulting firm in the Philippines, project managers are the essential link between the organization and its clients. Since their work is defined by the projects they lead, their commitment is vital for their company's success as they are the face of the firm to their clients.

One thing that needs to be highlighted is the high pressure to retain these professionals because technical roles are in such a great demand. Findings from the study of Aon (2025) have shown that IT and Sales both see a 24% increase in demand while AI roles follow at 21%. Such high demands create a competitive environment in which specialized project managers are the target of other firms. The concept of Perceived Organizational Support (POS) was defined by Eisenberger et al. (1986) as the belief that organization appreciates the contribution of its employees. When this support is felt, the employees usually respond with higher engagement. This is even more critical these days as new hire premiums for external talent have fallen into the range of 1.3% to 8.2%. The implication of this is that companies are no longer relying on salary bumps alone to attract or retain talent, but they have to be focused on internal support. If one analyzes the trend,

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the new hire premium dip means that the market is cooling but the 22.6% attrition rate means that people are still leaving. This pattern means that people aren't leaving for the money, but they are leaving because they are not getting the right support. The problem here is that there is an urgent need to safeguard the firm's talent pool from these external market pressures.

Organizational Commitment (OC) is the psychological bond that the employee has to his or her workplace. According to the model by Meyer and Allen (1991), this bond with the organization consists of three parts. These include affective commitment, which involves the emotional aspect; continuance commitment, which involves the economic aspect; and normative commitment, which involves the obligatory aspect. Understanding the effect of POS across these different areas is essential for developing proper human resource plans for the retention of such highly skilled talents. This study examined the relationship between POS and OC specifically among the project managers at Seven Seven Global Services, Inc. (77GSI), an IT consulting firm in the Philippines. What this study attempted to add is a contribution to both theoretical knowledge and practical management. The objective was to offer more effective means to lead and maintain project-based workforce in the current local market.

Background of the Study

Modern-day organizations are still experiencing ongoing difficulty in retaining important talent, and such pressure is felt more greatly in the Philippine consulting industry. Industry evidence shows that consulting in the Philippines has some of the highest projected attrition rates in the region, putting further urgency on the need for firms to maintain continuity in client delivery. In the field of IT consulting, Project Managers play

a central role in the stability of delivery by virtue of their retention of project knowledge, coordination of workstreams (inter-dependence of tasks) and representation of the firm to the client; their commitment to projects is a strategic asset, not simply an individual attitude. Modern project management research has shifted to a more "pluralistic" perspective on the field. Söderlund (2011) argues that the profession has undergone a paradigm shift from a narrow perspective on optimization to a wider perspective that includes human behavior, governance, and relationship schools of thought, such that the study of psychological constructs such as commitment is becoming more central to the success of the project.

As market conditions change and salary-based differentiation diminishes, it is becoming increasingly necessary for organizations to turn to internal support practices (in addition to compensation) to limit unnecessary attrition and maintain project leadership continuity.

Extensive research has been done on how organizations can ease the risks of turnover through internal support. Perceived Organizational Support (POS)—the employee's global belief that the organization values his or her contribution and cares about his or her well-being—has been consistently associated with favorable work outcomes. Anchored in Organizational Support Theory and backed by social exchange mechanisms, POS is expected to lead to reciprocity among employees through increased Organizational Commitment (OC), psychological bond conceptualized on the dimensions of affective (emotional), continuance (economic) and normative (obligatory). Reduced withdrawal tendencies have been generally associated with affective commitment tied to

POS, as supported by meta-analytic and empirical evidence (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002; Kurtessis et al., 2017).

However, POS is of unique consequence to the participants of this study because Project Managers in IT consulting are boundary spanners. In client-facing, project-based arrangements, Project Managers operate outside of stable reporting environments across organization boundaries. Boundary Spanning Theory explains that due to such roles, structurally exposed to role conflict and ambiguity as well as between the home organization and the client environment, support from the home organization becomes a critical buffer and a "psychological tether" that supports the maintenance of attachment to the parent firm while deployed externally. Consistent with a Job Demands-Resources framing, POS can be considered an important organizational resource, which buffers the experience of strain and maintains motivation under conditions of high project demands (e.g., time pressure, complex stakeholder ecosystems and unclear authority). In this sense, inadequate home organization support may increase the risks of detachment, double allegiance or lack of identification with the parent firm -- dynamics which may accelerate the turnover process in a sector that is already known for its high mobility.

This research addressed some of the important gaps in literature that may be grouped under both a Population Gap and a Knowledge Gap (Miles, 2017). Although POS and organizational commitment are long-established constructs used in the traditional employment setting, there is still little evidence specific to Project Managers in boundary-spanning, client-embedded arrangements - especially in the context of Philippine project-based IT consulting. In line with this gap the present study focused on Project Managers at 77GSI because of their boundary spanning responsibilities and hence cross

dependence on support from the home organization, and because of their sustained commitment are responsible for continuity of delivery and management of client relationships. In practical context, when a Project Manager disappears or leaves a project, the discontinuity that ensues can lead to downstream scope, cost, schedule and relationship risks for the client and the parent firm. Access to this group of respondents is possible because the researcher is included in 77GSI's Community of Practice PM Group allowing for legitimate access to the targeted group of professionals while ensuring proper ethical protocols for voluntary participation and confidentiality.

Further, some existing studies have tended to treat organizational commitment as an overall construct (Mowday et al., 1982; Porter et al., 1974; Mathieu & Zajac, 1990); this study addressed the need for knowledge by providing empirical data on the predictive validity of POS for overall OC and its three specific dimensions (affective, continuance and normative) in this particular context. By analyzing the relationship between POS and affective, continuance and normative commitment among Project Managers, the study was expected to provide evidence-based guidance which 77GSI can use to strengthen support practices and improve retention outcomes for this critical group—to help leadership identify if support most strongly influences the emotional attachment, perceived costs of leaving or felt obligation to remain.

Therefore, the aim of this quantitative study was to predict Organizational Commitment using Perceived Organizational Support for Project Manager at 77GSI. Using postpositivist world view and survey design, the extent to which POS was a statistical predictor of overall Organizational Commitment, affective commitment, continuance commitment and normative commitment was examined.

Theoretical Framework

Organizational Support Theory (OST) was the main theoretical framework of this study since the relationship between Perceived Organizational Support (POS) and Organizational Commitment (OC) was analyzed (Eisenberger et al., 1986; Rhoades and Eisenberger, 2002). The fundamental causal rationale of the study presented by OST was that employees who feel that their organization appreciates their efforts and are concerned about their welfare become more psychologically attached to the company. Although OST was used as the main framework, four supportive perspectives were also used to put the mechanisms and conditions under which this relationship functions based on the specific group of the population of the boundary-spanning project managers in Philippine IT consulting. These reinforcement frameworks were: Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964), the Three-Component Model of Organizational Commitment (Meyer and Allen, 1991), the Job Demands-Resources Model (Demerouti et al., 2001), and Boundary Spanning Theory (Aldrich and Herker, 1977). The supporting theories covered a particular dimension of the study setting, namely, reciprocity mechanisms, commitment dimensionality, resource-demand dynamics, and exposure to the structural role, respectively, whereas OST was the general explanatory model of the POS-OC predictive relationship.

Organizational Support Theory

For the theory that seems more feasible to this study, the researcher chose Organizational Support Theory (OST) which was able to provide the principal theoretical lens for understanding POS and its consequences (Eisenberger et al., 1986; Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002). OST proposes that employees develop a generalized belief about the extent to which the organization values their contributions and cares about their well-being

as employees. The global belief of POS starts to form in the mind of the employees and begins to influence how they understand and interpret the organization treats them through its policies, practices, and interactions with organizational agents such as supervisors and managers (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002; Kurtessis et al., 2017). So, when employees get a feeling that the organization they are part of cares about their welfare and recognizes their efforts, they begin to have an understanding the organization is willing to provide socioemotional and instrumental resources, especially when they are needed.

One of the main key points of OST suggests is that high POS fills an important socioemotional need such as the need for approval, self-esteem, and belongingness (Eisenberger et al., 1986; Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002). So, when an employee has POS, it also in turn strengthens performance-reward expectancies by signaling that good performance will be noticed and fairly rewarded. These processes and interaction are expected to lead to a stronger positive attitude toward the organization, especially the affective organizational commitment component, as well as higher engagement and discretionary efforts (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002; Kurtessis et al., 2017).

There is also a flipside version of this which is if employees have low POS, it is interpreted as indifference and neglect, which somehow affects the employees' sense of value and belonging and is likely to weaken their commitment to the organization.

Social Exchange Theory and the Norm of Reciprocity

Organizational Support Theory does not exist in a vacuum but is also tied to another theory which is the Social Exchange Theory. Social Exchange Theory (SET) tells

us that relationships evolve over time into trusting, loyal, and mutual commitments as long as the parties follow by the rules of exchange, such as the norm of reciprocity (Blau, 1964; Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005). So, for an employee that works for a company who perceives that their company provides support, fairness, and care that goes beyond contractual obligations, they feel an obligation to reciprocate with positive attitudes and behaviors that benefit the organization (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005; Eisenberger et al., 2001).

Having established the norm of reciprocity, a key mechanism has been identified that links Perceived Organizational Support (POS) to organizational commitment. Employees who perceive high organizational support will tend to feel some indebtedness and motivated to respond with stronger emotional attachment, identification, and willingness to exert effort on the organization's behalf (Eisenberger et al., 2001; Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002). In collectivist cultures, the sense of mutual obligation is even more evident, and maintaining harmonious relationships is given high importance (Hofstede, 2001). So, in this type of context with collectivist cultures, high POS is likely to translate not only into stronger affective commitment but also a higher normative commitment, reflected in a felt duty to remain and contribute to the organization.

Three-Component Model of Organizational Commitment

This study adopted the widely used three-component model of organizational commitment that was conceived by Meyer and Allen (1991, 1997), which conceptualizes commitment as composed of affective, continuance, and normative dimensions. Affective commitment refers to an employee's involvement in the organization, the desire to be identified with the institution, and a significant emotional attachment to it. It captures the

psychological state where an individual chooses to remain with the employer because they truly want to do so (Allen & Meyer, 1990; Meyer & Allen, 1997). On the other end, continuance commitment is about staying because one needs to, which involves reflecting on the perceived costs of leaving the company, loss of company benefits, leaving the established social networks, and even limited alternative for job opportunities (Meyer & Allen, 1991). Normative commitment on the other hand talks about a felt obligation to remain with the company, often rooted in moral or relational obligations, it reflects staying because one feels ought to or obligated to (Meyer & Allen, 1997).

According to Meyer et al. (2002), based on empirical research, affective commitment is the preferred form of commitment on the perspective of an organization because it is consistently associated with higher performance, lower turnover intentions, and greater extra-role behaviors. The opposite of this is the continuance commitment because it was found to be weaker or sometimes even negative associations with desirable outcomes, while normative commitment tends to be on the middle-ground (Meyer et al., 2002). On the lens of the OST, it will specifically predict that POS will be most strongly linked to affective commitment because a perceived care and valuing of contributions directly nurture emotional attachment and identification (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002; Kurtessis et al., 2017). Another thing to note is that POS may also enhance normative commitment through a sense of moral obligation, indebtedness, or the need to reciprocate, especially in the context of relational and collectivist cultures, whereas its relationship with continuance commitment is expected to be indirect or weak (Meyer & Allen, 1997; Eisenberger et al., 2001).

Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model

As a way to further give context and supplement the role of POS in high-pressure work environments, the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model offers a complementary theoretical framework (Demerouti et al., 2001; Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). This JD-R model classifies job characteristics into demands, like those aspects of work that require sustained effort and are associated with physiological and psychological costs, examples are workload, time pressure, role ambiguity, and interpersonal conflicts as well as physiological and psychological resource, those that help achieve work goals, reduce demands, and stimulate personal growth and development such as autonomy, feedback, and support.

In this JD-R framework, POS works as a higher-order job resource (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007; Kurtessis et al., 2017). POS enhances motivational processes by signaling that the organization will provide those resources like assistance, recognition, and flexibility when needed, which in turn will increase work engagement and commitment. While this is happening, POS can also buffer the negative impact of high job demands on strain and burnout by reassuring employees that they are not facing challenges alone (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007).

Project managers are frequently dealing with tight deadlines, complex stakeholder expectations, and unclear authority and responsibilities. In this light, organizational support can determine what is happening under high demands. With strong support, demands may help to create engagement and commitment. This can result in exhaustion and disengagement if without solid support.

Boundary Spanning Theory

Another theory used to supplement this paper is the Boundary Spanning Theory. It emphasizes roles and processes that connect an organization to the external environment. It describes the relationship between some actors linking internal units with external stakeholders. These actors also convey information and bargain on expectations across organizational boundaries (Aldrich & Herker, 1977; Tushman, 1977).

Boundary spanners are people responsible for scanning the environment, translating and filtering information, and reconciling sometimes conflicting demands between their home organization and external parties (Marchington, Vincent, & Cooke, 2005). In inter-organizational arrangements—such as outsourcing, consulting, and contracting, consultants or contractors not only manage information flows but also maintain relationships and uphold contractual and relational obligations on behalf of their parent organization (Marchington, Vincent, & Cooke, 2005).

This positions the respondents of this study, the project managers, as the consultants that are deployed in client-based settings who perfectly fit the profile of boundary spanners, highlighting that they operate at the interface between the IT consulting firm and the client organization, simultaneously representing the interests, values, and support of the home firm while adapting to the norms of the requirements of the client.

That is why it is worth noting this theory as one of the lenses to look at on this research as this gave a special flavor distinct from all the other studies and enriched our interpretation on how perceived organizational support from the home organization is

experienced by the project managers who are structurally embedded in client environments, and how such boundary-spanning work shapes their organizational commitment.

The aspect of dual organizational identification is especially applicable in the boundary-spanning setting within the scope of this research. Based on Social Identity Theory (Tajfel & Turner, 1979; Ashforth and Mael, 1989), it has been found that workers in inter-organizational systems can both be affiliated with their own company, as well as the client company (Vora and Kostova, 2007). Webber (2011) discovered that managers of IT projects who were dual identified had greater personal attachment and client loyalty. This dual identification dynamic was particularly important to 77GSI project managers who were in client locations where it was theorized that POS in the home organization was critical: it was the major mechanism through which home-firm identification was maintained and that identity drift would not occur towards the client organization.

The idea of dual organizational identification, which was initially inspired by Social Identity Theory (Tajfel and Turner, 1979; Ashforth and Mael, 1989), was incorporated into the discussion of boundaries, without being discussed as a theoretical lens on its own. Under boundary-spanning, project managers can have dual identities with the mother consulting organization and the client organization (Vora and Kostova, 2007; Webber, 2011). This two-identification dynamic proved pertinent in understanding how POS of the home organization-maintained commitment despite the fact that the project managers were socially situated in client environments. Nevertheless, since the nature of this study did not involve the actual measurement of organizational identification, this construct was

framed as a situational aspect of Boundary Spanning Theory, as opposed to a theoretical pillar of its own.

Operational Framework

This research focused on the causality of Perceived Organizational Support (POS) and Organizational Commitment (OC) of project managers in 77GSI. Grounded in Organizational Support Theory and the ex-post facto research tradition, the study examined the POS as antecedent variables (X) and OC as the outcome variables (O) in the form of $X \rightarrow O$ (Campbell & Stanley, 1963; Cohen et al., 2018).

Perceived Organizational Support (POS) is operationalized as the belief that the company values the contributions of its employees and cares about their well-being (Eisenberger et al., 1986). Organizational Commitment (OC) is operationalized by the Three-Component Model (Meyer & Allen, 1991) which has three dimensions: affective, continuance, and normative.

Figure 1

Operational Framework Showing the Relationship Between Perceived Organizational Support and Organizational Commitment

This operational framework analyzes the linking variable between the Perceived Organizational Support (POS) and the Organizational Commitment of a project manager. The study used a causal research design (co-relational study under the ex post facto framework) in which POS was considered as antecedent variable (X) and organizational commitment as outcome variable (O) and represented as $X \rightarrow O$ (Campbell & Stanley, 1963; Cohen et al., 2018).

Consistent with an ex-post facto methodology, this design assumed a direction causal pathway in which the antecedent variable, POS, comes before and predicts the present condition of OC (Cohen et al., 2018). To assess this relationship, the two variables were both measured exactly as they would occur in the natural world and were not systematically manipulated by the researcher (Nesselroade & Grimm, 2019).

On the right-hand side is Organizational Commitment (OC), which is anchored in the Three-Component Model by Meyer and Allen (1991). This framework is further supported by the meta-analytic studies of Meyer et al. (2002), where OC is operationalized through three distinct components: affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment. In accordance with the causal research design of the study, the constructs were linked by a directional arrow to indicate that POS was modeled as the causal antecedent of OC where the independent variable was measured as naturally occurring phenomenon to find its effect on the dependent outcome.

Statement of the Problem

The main problem this study sought to answer was: Is Perceived Organizational Support (POS) a significant predictor of Organizational Commitment among Project Managers at 77GSI?

More specifically, the study aimed to achieve the following objectives:

1. Determine the level of Perceived Organizational Support among project managers at 77GSI using the items of SPOS.
2. Determine the level of Organizational Commitment among project managers at 77GSI using the following dimensions:
 - 2.1. Affective Commitment;
 - 2.2. Continuance Commitment; and
 - 2.3. Normative Commitment
3. Determine if Perceived Organizational Support significantly predicts overall Organizational Commitment among project managers at 77GSI.

4. Determine if Perceived Organizational Support significantly predicts each component of organizational commitment, namely affective, continuance, and normative commitment among project managers at 77GSI.

Statement of Hypothesis

Following conventional statistical practice, the study presented its hypotheses in the null form (H_0); the basic assumption was that no significant predictive relationship existed between the variables. The alternative hypothesis (H_1) which is supported by the theoretical framework and literature review assumed that the Perceived Organizational Support was a significant causal antecedent of Organizational Commitment. While the nature of the study was of a causal research design ($X \rightarrow O$) to examine the directional relationships as they happen naturally (Cohen et al., 2018). The hypothesis statements were tested as statistical predictions based on the observed data under the ex post facto framework. The following null hypotheses were tested:

H₀1: POS does not significantly predict overall OC among the project managers at 77GSI.

H₀2: POS does not significantly predict Affective Commitment among the project managers at 77GSI.

H₀3: POS does not significantly predict Continuance Commitment among the project managers at 77GSI.

H₀4: POS does not significantly predict Normative Commitment among the project managers at 77GSI.

Scope and Delimitations of the Study

The current research problem adopted the causal research design (co-relational study in the paradigm of ex-post facto research) based on a postpositivist worldview, whereby the researcher tested objective hypothesis by analyzing the directional relationship between the variables as they exist in nature (Cohen et al., 2018; Creswell & Creswell, 2023). This non-experimental approach studies the cause-and-effect relationship between variables without manipulating them - a quality that is reserved for true experimental designs. Specifically, Perceived Organizational Support (POS) is the independent variable (X) which temporally precedes Organizational Commitment (OC), the dependent outcome (O) in the form of $X \rightarrow O$ (Campbell & Stanley, 1963; Cohen et al., 2018, pp. 420-421). The objective is to establish the extent with which POS causally predicts the three dimensions of OC (affective, continuance, and normative) among project managers at 77GSI.

Consistent with the deductive approach and quantitative research tradition, this study employed a census (total population sampling) approach. The target population consisted of all eligible Project Managers at 77GSI ($N = 75$) after the researcher was excluded from participation to avoid bias. Because the population was small, finite, and fully accessible, all eligible individuals were invited to participate rather than drawing a random sample. This approach eliminated sampling error and ensured complete representation of the target population (Cohen et al., 2018; Sevilla et al., 1992). All 75 eligible Project Managers participated, yielding a 100% response rate.

Data collection involved the use of validated instruments, the 8 item Survey of Perceived Organizational Support (SPOS) for the independent variable and the 18 item

Three-Component Model (TCM) Employee Commitment Survey for the dependent variable, administered through online self-report questionnaire.

The research was strictly delimited to Project Managers deployed in client sites of 77GSI's Philippine operation at the time of data collection. Findings were interpreted within this specific context and generalization for other consulting firms, industries, or cultural contexts needed to be further empirically validated. As a cross-sectional design was used, the data collection was at one point in time, the causal relation between POS and OC as they naturally occur without following a longitudinal approach.

Consistent with Cohen et al. (2018), in this study there was no experimental manipulation but rather a research design of causal research supporting directional inferences ($X \rightarrow O$) in accordance with the ex post facto nature. The researcher strictly kept focus on the POS-OC causal pathway, and other variables, like leadership quality, compensation structures, job demands and client-site environmental factors were ruled out as primary predictors.

Another limitation is related to the disclosure of a token of gratitude to the two organizational decision makers, the PMO Manager and the Client Delivery Manager, who gave their permission to the researcher to proceed with the study. The token was only offered to these decision makers as a token of their gatekeeping role as recorded in Appendix H and no tokens, incentives or compensation of any nature was offered to the participating project managers, whose involvement was voluntary and anonymous throughout. However, the researcher also admits that the announcement of a gatekeeper token might have also had an indirect effect on organizational openness to the study or

communicated support of participation and this subsequently could have affected response rates. Results must be thus understood with respect to this contextual consideration.

Significance of the Study

This study tested the significance of Perceived Organizational Support (POS) as a predictor to Organizational Commitment (OC) for project managers at 77GSI. Much has been written in organizational research about the relationship between POS and commitment. Evidence is still limited, though, in project-based, staff augmentation settings.

In such situations, project managers are boundary spanners. For instance, they are used by a consulting firm but integrated into a client environment. This arrangement can cause uncertainty about who the source of perceived support is, the home firm or the client. It can also make it difficult to determine where organizational commitment is directed.

This study considers POS in the context of the three components of OC namely affective, continuance, and normative commitment. By concentrating on the IT consulting firm context, the research offers context-specific information that can help to inform targeted retention and support practices for project managers in Philippine consulting organizations.

This study was significant to the following groups:

Senior Leaders and Organizational Executives. The findings indicated that Perceived Organizational Support (POS) has predictive power towards Organizational Commitment (OC) of project managers at 77GSI. The study also identified the most sensitive component of OC to POS: affective, continuance, or normative. This evidence can help leaders focus on support practices that will help build commitment and reduce unwanted attrition. It also provides a focused and credible basis for decision making around recognition, resource support, and communication cadence and support during escalations.

Human Resources Practitioners and Organizational Development Practitioners. For HR and OD practitioners, the results can be used to guide training programs to increase the Perceived Organizational Support (POS) and commitment. This is particularly true for project managers working in a client environment. This study can be utilized by HR and OD teams as empirical evidence for more appropriate training needs analysis and manager capability building. The findings will also help when it comes to improvements as part of onboarding, or even the design of performance systems, and even internal mobility pathways. In practice, interventions can be aimed at supporting cues that are predictive of commitment. This helps avoid overreliance on broad engagement activities.

People Managers, Delivery Leaders, and PMO or Practice Leads. The results can be used in day-to-day management behaviors that can enhance perceived support. These behaviors include giving prompt feedback, managing escalations, negotiating workload and providing consistent advocacy for resources. The results also explain the relationship between POS and OC. Regular check-ins, coaching loops, conflict-

management and issue-resolution can be for consideration during governance routines. When a project manager is under constant delivery pressure, these routines may be able to provide the support needed.

Project Managers. These findings can help project managers describe organizational support in a manner that can be measured. They also explain the relationship of support to commitment. The recommendations assist project managers in communicating their support requirements and expectations with leaders. These strategies also serve the purpose of boundary-spanning work. They help the project managers to remain attached to the home organization while operating beyond organizational boundaries.

The Philippine IT Consulting Industry. The results of this research provided evidence on the importance of organizational support in maintaining workforce commitment at the sector level in the Philippine IT consulting industry. As the projected attrition rates were to hit 22.6% (Aon, 2025) the industry was under pressure to find internal retention levers outside of compensation. This study offered empirical evidence of the strategic value of organizational support practices as a retention mechanism in the Philippine consulting setting by showing that POS explained 46.1% of the variance in Overall Organizational Commitment among project managers in a staff augmentation firm. These results can guide human capital practices at the industry level, benchmarking initiatives, and workforce planning models of the IT consulting firms in the Philippines and the overall ASEAN region.

Clients of IT Consulting Firms. The findings also had practical implications for the client organizations who were dependent on the IT consulting firms delivering projects. Since project managers used to be the main contact point between the consulting firm and the client, they impacted continuity of delivery, institutional knowledge preservation and relationship stability directly. The study showed that project managers who felt well supported by 77GSI, in terms of organization support, were more likely to show increased affective and normative commitment - lessening the chances of mid-project disillusionment that might interfere with client operations. Client organizations might thus be interested in knowing how the internal practices of their consulting partners in terms of support contributed to the quality and stability of the project team engaged on their engagements.

Academic Researchers. To the scholarly community, this work provided empirical evidence on the POS-OC association in a population that was underrepresented in the research on organizational behavior: boundary-spanning project managers of client-embedded, staff augmentation arrangements. The paper addressed a population gap and a knowledge gap (Miles, 2017) as it was testing pre-existing constructs in an environment that exhibited structural ambiguity in terms of organizational boundaries. The result that Normative Commitment was the most strongly predicted dimension ($b = 0.780$), provided a culturally informed insight that Affective Commitment would be dominant, giving future researchers a ground by which comparative studies of the POS-OC relationship can be made across cultures. The article also indicated the relevance of Boundary Spanning Theory (Aldrich and Herker, 1977; Marchington et al., 2005) to support dynamics in project-based consulting which was a field that had not been well developed theoretically in project management literature.

Definition of Terms

Some terminologies that explain the central ideas of this study are:

Affective Commitment - shows emotional attachment and identification with the organization. Employees stay because they want to. A feeling of belonging and personal identification with organizational goals facilitates such attachment (Allen & Meyer, 1990).

Boundary Spanner - A boundary spanner works at the boundary between the home organization and the external parties. This role is in the exchange of information and coordination of relationships (Aldrich & Herker, 1977). In this case, project managers at 77GSI serve as boundary spanners between the consulting firm and the client.

Consulting Firm – A consulting firm provides specialized services to client organizations under contractual arrangements. In this study, the IT consulting firm refers to the company that employs project managers and assigns them to client engagements.

Continuance Commitment - reflects the costs of leaving. Employees remain because they have to. These costs can be financial loss, reduced benefits, disrupted career plans or fewer job alternatives (Meyer & Allen, 1991).

Dual Organizational Identification – Dual organizational identification refers to simultaneous identification with, and attachment to, two organizations. In this study, the two referents are the IT consulting firm and the client organization where deployment occurs, such as BDO Unibank, Inc. (Vora & Kostova, 2007).

Indebtedness / Felt Obligation – means the mental condition where one has a moral or relationship obligation to give back support, care or resources offered by the

organization. Unlike transactional reciprocity, felt obligation in collectivist societies like the Philippines exists as a lasting moral relationship as opposed to an exchange. This measure was applicable in the current research to understand the influence of POS that was a good predictor of Normative Commitment (Eisenberger et al., 2001; Meyer and Allen, 1997).

Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Model – a theoretical model that classifies work characteristics into demands (aspects requiring sustained effort and associated with physiological or psychological costs) and resources (aspects that help achieve work goals, reduce demands, and stimulate growth). In this study, POS was conceptualized as a higher-order organizational resource that buffered the negative impact of high project demands on strain and sustained motivational processes (Demerouti et al., 2001; Bakker & Demerouti, 2007).

Normative Commitment - represents a sense of obligation to stay. Employees stay because they feel as if they should. This obligation may grow out of perceived organizational investment, norms of loyalty or expectations of reciprocity (Meyer & Allen, 1997).

Organizational Commitment (OC) - refers to an employee's psychological attachment to an organization and intention to be a member (Mowday et al., 1982). I conceptualize OC using the Three-Component Model (Meyer and Allen, 1991, 1997). This model involves affective, continuance and normative commitment.

Organizational Support Theory (OST) – the theoretical perspective suggesting that employees develop a generalized belief concerning the degree to which their

organization appreciates their contribution and is concerned about their well-being and that the belief (POS) is an antecedent to their attitudes, behaviors and commitments to the organization (Eisenberger et al., 1986; Rhoades and Eisenberger, 2002). The main theoretical framework of this research was OST.

Perceived Organizational Support (POS) - POS is the employee's overall belief that the organization appreciates what he or she has to offer and cares about them as a person (Eisenberger et al., 1986). In this study, POS is a unidimensional construct. Measurement is based on the Survey of Perceived Organizational Support (SPOS) for the perception of organizational valuing, care, and support.

Project-Based Organization – A project-based organization structures work primarily through projects rather than purely functional operations. Work is delivered through time-bound engagements led by project managers. In this study, the IT consulting firm is treated as project-based because delivery is organized around discrete client projects and programs.

Project Manager - The professional that performs the act of leading the end-to-end planning through closure to achieve goals within constraint such as scope, schedule and cost. In this study, the term is used to refer to employees of 77GSI assigned to client sites to lead or support consulting assignments.

Social Exchange Theory (SET) – a model that describes how social relationships are formed as a reciprocal process, in which individuals give benefits to each other, depending on the likelihood of payback. In the organizational setting, SET assumes that, once employees feel that the organization is supporting them, they have a sense of

obligation to respond by being more committed and putting in discretionary effort (Blau, 1964; Cropanzano and Mitchell, 2005).

Social Identity Theory (SIT) – a theory of how people get at least some of their self-concept through belonging to social groups and organizations, and how self-identification has an influence on their attitudes and behaviors (Tajfel and Turner, 1979; Ashforth and Mael, 1989). SIT was mentioned in the context of dual organizational identification of project managers who worked at the boundary in this study.

Utang na Loob – a Filipino cultural aspect which means the debt of gratitude or the debt of the inner self. It is described as a personalized sense of duty to pay back that which one has benefited from others, especially that which seems to be voluntary or even more than what is imposed by a contract. Ultimately, in the organizational setting, *utang na loob* can increase the level of normative commitment in the event that employees feel that there are real organizational care and concern about their well-being (Jocano, 1997; Enriquez, 1992).

CHAPTER II:

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

In this chapter, a detailed literature review of the research's two main constructs—Perceived Organizational Support (POS) and Organizational Commitment (OC)—is provided. The review is organized into three primary sections: first, the concept of POS is addressed, covering its definition, theoretical background, antecedents, outcomes, and measurement. Second, Organizational Commitment is discussed at the construct level, followed by three subsections detailing its dimensions: affective, continuance, and normative. Third, the empirical association between POS and OC is investigated across a variety of settings, highlighting studies that both support and dispute this relationship. The review then summarized the meta-analytic results of POS and organization performance, assessed turnover and attrition patterns in IT consulting and BPO industry, and summarized POS-related HR interventions to retain employees. The chapter ends by determining the gap in research that was filled by the current one.

Perceived Organizational Support (POS)

Perceived Organizational Support (POS) is defined as the global beliefs of employees regarding the degree of value that their organization places on their contributions and concern for their well-being (Eisenberger et al., 1986). This construct is grounded in Organizational Support Theory (OST), which posits that employees develop generalized perceptions about the organization's commitment to them based on how they are treated by organizational agents and the organization's policies and practices.

The development of POS theory can be traced to the work of Eisenberger and colleagues in the mid-1980s. Eisenberger et al. (1986) proposed that employees form global beliefs about the organization's commitment to them, and these beliefs influence employees' attitudes and behaviors toward the organization. This view positions POS as the organizational counterpart to employee commitment, that is, the organization's perceived commitment to the employee rather than the employee's commitment to the organization.

Over the past three decades, POS theory has evolved and been refined through extensive empirical work. Rhoades and Eisenberger (2002) conducted an influential meta-analysis that confirmed the central role of POS in organizational behavior. More recently, Kurtessis et al. (2017) offered an updated meta-analytic assessment of Organizational Support Theory, further supporting the importance of the construct and identifying key antecedents and consequences. Eisenberger et al. (2020) reported that the average level of perceived support has increased slightly over the past three decades and that, notably, the positive effects of POS appear to be even stronger in Eastern, collectivist cultures than in Western, individualist cultures.

Although POS is generally considered unidimensional construct, studies have identified two expanding functional areas. The first area is the socioemotional support, which includes showing care, concern, respect, and pride towards employees. The second area is instrumental support, which encompasses provision of material resources, conflict support, decision latitude and support in coping with work demands (Rhoades and Eisenberger, 2002; Kurtessis et al., 2017).

There is a significant difference between POS and other related yet conceptually different constructs like perceived supervisor support. Despite the fact that supervisors are usually the most visible agents of the organization, employees are able to tell the difference between support that comes about as a result of personal disposition of a supervisor and support that comes about as a result of organizational policies, values and commitments (Eisenberger et al., 2002). Within the project-based work environment, project sponsors, project management offices or senior management actions can be perceived by project managers as key messages regarding the support of the organization.

Antecedents of POS

Studies have established a number of important antecedents of POS. Among the noteworthy aspects are that Perceived fairness-distributive, procedural, and interactional justice - is an influential factor. Employees tend to believe that the organization is interested in their welfare when they feel that decisions made are fair, transparent and respectful (Rhoades and Eisenberger, 2002; Colquitt, 2001). Supervisor support plays a central role in the development of POS as well; the supervisors who give feedback, demonstrate consideration, and support their subordinates are viewed to be communicating the wider organizational support (Eisenberger et al., 2002). Also, positive job conditions and rewards, including competitive pay, development, job security, and safe working conditions lead to increased POS as employees respond to organizational concern when such conditions are perceived to be intentional (Rhoades and Eisenberger, 2002; Kurtessis et al., 2017).

The impact of organizational support has also been documented in the areas of organizational performance and technological adaptation. Jeong and Kim (2022) found that POS has a positive effect on organizational performance by reducing perceptions of differential treatment and fostering a fair, supportive environment. Furthermore, Li et al. (2021) demonstrated that POS serves as a key moderator between technological change awareness and turnover intention, thereby protecting employees from the job insecurity that can accompany the adoption of new technologies such as artificial intelligence and robotics.

Outcomes of POS

A substantial body of empirical literature, including multiple meta-analyses, has documented the significant positive effects of POS on a variety of employee attitudes and behaviors. Higher POS has been consistently associated with higher affective organizational commitment, higher overall organizational commitment, greater job satisfaction, lower turnover intentions, and stronger organizational identification (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002; Riggle et al., 2009; Kurtessis et al., 2017). POS has also been linked to increases in in-role performance, organizational citizenship behavior, and reduced absenteeism (Riggle et al., 2009; Kurtessis et al., 2017).

Previous studies indicate enormous evidence of the correlation between the work environment and long-term commitment. Naz et al. (2020) showed that the working environment was positively and significantly influential on employee retention, and organizational commitment is a significant mediator between the environmental factors and the intention to stay. Tjahjono et al. (2020) discovered that both POS and

organizational commitment had a greater effect on improving employee performance and willingness to work more efficiently, showing that organizational commitment is not only a retention measure but also a success factor of an organization.

Recent research has further expanded the understanding of POS outcomes. Maan et al. (2020) found that POS was positively associated with job satisfaction and organizational commitment, with psychological empowerment partially mediating this relationship. Silva et al. (2022) demonstrated that POS had both direct and indirect effects on affective organizational commitment through the mediating role of job satisfaction. In the healthcare sector, El Akremi et al. (2021) found that organizational support increased affective commitment and decreased turnover among nurses at both the individual and team levels. Sherwani et al. (2023) established that POS and employee loyalty mediated the relationship between leadership effectiveness and task performance.

Measurement of POS

The Survey of Perceived Organizational Support (SPOS) by Eisenberger et al. (1986) is the most commonly used to measure POS. The initial version was composed of 36 questions in assessing the degree to which employees think that the organization cares about them and is appreciative of their input. It was later reduced to a shorter 8 item version to minimize the burden on respondents without compromising on reliability and validity (Eisenberger et al., 2001). The shortened SPOS has shown good internal consistency whereby the Cronbach alpha values usually go beyond the figure of .90 (Worley et al., 2009). The 8-item SPOS was used and produced a Cronbach's alpha of .892 thus validating its reliability in this sample.

POS in the Philippine Context

The SPOS has been used to investigate Filipino employees in local government and has been directly adopted and shown to have acceptable psychometric properties (Andrin & Dumale, 2023). The definition of organizational support in the Philippines is tightly connected with the local personality traits and social conventions. The Filipino personality has been marked by a strong interpersonal harmony and relationship sensitivity as emphasized by Church (1986). This mindset is transferred to the workplace in the form of paternalistic expectations, in which employees tend to think of the organization in terms of family, and the focus on personal well-being by leadership is greatly appreciated.

Alampay (2014) noted that human resource practices in the Philippines are often a combination of formal policy and informal, relationship-based commitments. This cultural subtlety was traced in empirical research; to illustrate, Artatanaya et al. (2023) have shown that even simple indications of an organizational appreciation of the input of employees could predict commitment significantly even in small-to-medium enterprise environments. These results indicate that the construct of POS might have special significance in the Filipino work setting, where relational and moral aspects of assistance overlap professional expectations.

Organizational Commitment (OC)

Organizational Commitment is defined as the psychological attachment employees feel toward their organization, reflected in their willingness to exert effort on behalf of the organization and their desire to maintain membership in it (Mowday et al.,

1982). This construct has been researched extensively in organizational behavior and human resource management due to its significant relationships with important work outcomes.

Organizational commitment has evolved greatly in regard to its conceptualization. The early studies considered commitment as a unidimensional variable that was mainly involved with affective attachment. Subsequently, however, theoretical work recognized the multidimensionality of commitment and more subtle conceptualizations arose. In 1991 and 1997, Meyer and Allen developed the Three-Component Model (TCM) that became the most popular model of organizational commitment. This model conceptualizes commitment as having three dimensions, the affective, continuance and normative commitment.

Based on a great deal of empirical evidence, Meyer et al. (2002) determined that affective commitment is a more desirable type of commitment according to an organizational standpoint since it is always linked with increased performance, reduced turnover desires and increased extra-role actions. Continuance commitment shows some weak and occasionally negative correlations with desirable outcomes, whereas normative commitment tends to be intermediate.

Organizational commitment has a number of established tools of measurement. One of the first and most popular scales, originally designed to be a global measure, with a focus on affective commitment, was the Organizational Commitment Questionnaire (OCQ) created by Mowday et al. (1982). Even in recent studies, the TCM scales that were created by Meyer and Allen (1997) are still the tool of choice. The TCM tool has 18 items,

each dimension having six items. Past research has indicated good reliability levels with Cronbach alpha coefficients of an average of .85 in affective commitment, .79 in continuance commitment and .73 in normative commitment (Meyer et al., 1993). In the current paper, the scales of TCM have provided Cronbach alpha of affective commitment, continuance commitment, normative commitment and overall organizational commitment of 0.819, 0.883 and 0.888 respectively.

Such a multidimensional approach is particularly beneficial when one wants to learn about employees in the environment where relational norms and obligations play a major role. Affective and normative commitment can overlap significantly in the case of the Philippines, where cultural values tend to be more collectivist, respect hierarchy, and where *pakikisama* (smooth interpersonal relations) and *utang na loob* (debt of gratitude), are practiced. Feeling taken care of by the organization can also give employees a moral obligation towards the organization to give back by remaining and contributing (Hofstede, 2001; Jocano, 1997).

Affective Commitment (AC)

Affective commitment is the emotional attachment, identification, and involvement in the organization. High affective commitment employees stay in the organization due to their desire to do so. This dimension portrays a good affective attachment which is typified by belongingness, loyalty and identification with organizational goals and values (Allen and Meyer, 1990; Meyer and Allen, 1997).

Affective commitment is typically considered most desirable commitment in terms of organizational viewpoint since it is always associated with positive results in increased

performance, decreased turnover intentions, increased organizational citizenship behavior, and reduced absenteeism (Meyer et al., 2002). When employees are highly affectively committed, they are truly interested in working towards organizational success due to their emotional involvement in the organization.

The high correlation between POS and affective commitment in a wide range of settings has been supported by empirical evidence. Positively, POS based on the measured SPOS was related to the organizational commitment of local government employees in the Philippine context (Andrin and Dumale, 2023). Cross-industrial studies of Indonesian organizations in the hospitality, manufacturing, small and medium enterprises, and the public sector consistently reported that POS positively influenced organizational or affective commitment, and sometimes, job satisfaction and affective commitment played mediating roles (Cahaya and Rahyuda, 2019; Febriantoro, 2018; Nurfayani and Wibawa, 2022; Astuty & Udin, 2020; Renggi & Yudhistira, 2024; Diana & Satrya, 2024).

The mediation processes by which POS converts to affective commitment have been further expounded in more recent studies. Silva et al. (2022) proved that POS influenced both directly and indirectly affective organizational commitment, as job satisfaction provided a significant mediating variable. Maan et al. (2020) discovered that this relationship was partially mediated by psychological empowerment meaning that once employees are supported, they tend to become more empowered, which consequently strengthens their psychological bond with the organization. Ullah et al. (2020) also observed that POS also helped in influencing affective commitment through the

development of prosocial motivation that helped to create a motivational work environment where employees became more inclined to participate in extra-role behaviors.

The result of actual proactive workplace behaviors beyond simple attachment have also been connected to support perceptions. Sakarina et al. (2023) established that POS facilitated the occurrence of organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) by the mediating role of organizational commitment, which supports the belief that commitment is not an attitude of staying but a motivation channel where organizational support is transformed into discretionary effort and helping behaviors. Alshaabani et al. (2021) discovered that POS positively influenced organizational citizenship behavior among Hungarian employees during the COVID-19 pandemic, and the effect of the affective commitment was an important mediating variable.

Continuance Commitment (CC)

Continuance commitment is the feeling of the expenses incurred by quitting the organization. High continuance employees are where they are due to necessity. This dimension is based on the investments that employees have made in the organization like contribution to pension schemes, benefits that are vested over time and specialized skills that they have and the perceived inability to find similar alternative employment (Allen and Meyer, 1990; Meyer and Allen, 1991).

Continuance commitment is generally regarded as less desirable than affective commitment and has been linked to weaker or sometimes even negative associations with desirable outcomes (Meyer et al., 2002). Employees who remain primarily because of perceived exit costs may be less motivated to perform at high levels and may exhibit

withdrawal behaviors. From the perspective of Organizational Support Theory, POS is expected to be only indirectly or weakly related to continuance commitment because this dimension is based on perceived costs of leaving rather than on emotional bonds or feelings of being valued (Meyer & Allen, 1997; Eisenberger et al., 2001).

However, even with a supportive organization, there is a possibility of an indirect impact on continuance commitment. The perceived cost of the departure can be increased by organizational investments in employee development, competitive benefits and project-specific training. The support infrastructure provided by the organization such as the escalation channels, resource advocacy and career development facilities may be cumulative investments to the home firm that need to be included in a cost-based attachment to the home firm.

Normative Commitment (NC)

Normative commitment is the sense of duty to stay in the organization. Employees with high normative commitment stay because they feel that they are obligated to do so. This dimension is a sense of moral or relational duty that can be brought about by a perception of organizational investment, norms of loyalty or expectations of reciprocity (Meyer and Allen, 1997).

Normative commitment is likely to hold a mid-range position between affective and continuance commitment in terms of its associations with the work outcomes (Meyer et al., 2002). Highly committed employees through their normative commitment might be driven to give back to the organization yet such commitment might not come with the same level of emotional attachment as those associated with affective commitment. Moral

obligation, indebtedness and perceived obligation to reciprocate are some of the mechanisms that POS can increase normative commitment, especially in relational cultures and collectivist cultures (Meyer and Allen, 1997; Eisenberger et al., 2001).

The Filipino cultural notion of *utang na loob* (debt of gratitude) can be of specific importance in enhancing the relationship between POS and normative commitment. To the Philippines, any form of support, or investment by an organization can trigger an internally strong feeling of moral obligation that goes beyond the formal employment contract. In cases where the employees feel that the organization has invested in their career, well-being or professional development, *utang na loob* develops a psychological sense of obligation that will encourage them to remain a part of the organization and contribute. This cultural interaction provides a viable reason as to why normative commitment levels can be particularly high with Filipino workers who feel well supported by the organization (Hofstede, 2001; Jocano, 1997).

The Relationship of POS and OC

The theoretical connection of the relation between POS and organizational commitment has been established well out of numerous past studies. Organizational Support Theory assumes that affective commitment is the most closely related to POS since the care and appreciation of the contribution employees make by the organization directly contributes to emotional attachment and identification (Rhoades and Eisenberger, 2002; Kurtessis et al., 2017). Social Exchange Theory also incorporates that where employees feel they are being assisted beyond the contractual duties then they feel obliged to respond with good attitudes and behaviors, such as greater commitment (Cropanzano and Mitchell, 2005). This perceived sense of reciprocity is also enhanced in

the collectivist cultures through the cultural focus on relational harmony and interpersonal reciprocity (Hofstede, 2001).

The relationship between POS-OC has been extensively analyzed in a variety of organizational contexts, with most of the studies showing a positive relationship, but some opposing results have also arisen. In this section, a critical analysis of the empirical evidence is presented to include the abundant literature that has shown the existence of the POS-OC relationship and the studies that have refuted or moderated it.

Empirical Evidence Supporting the POS-OC Link

There is significant empirical evidence that demonstrates the positive association between POS and organizational commitment. In the Philippine setting, Andrin et al. (2023) showed a positive significant relationship between organizational support and organizational commitment among employees of the City Hall of Surigao, with the higher the organizational support, the higher the commitment levels. Singh et al. (2024) examined professional organizations in finance and technology industries and discovered that POS positively affected organizational commitment with significant correlations among the constructs.

Predictive capability of POS has been shown to be cross-cultural. Donald et al. (2016) studied the role of POS in South African higher education institutions and found that POS had significant positive relationships with job satisfaction and organizational commitment (median job satisfaction between POS and OC). Pattnaik et al. (2020) discovered that POS made a considerable impact on the organizational commitment of corporate executives in Indian manufacturing firms. The cross-cultural applicability of

Organizational Support Theory was revealed as Zhang and Li (2022) revealed that POS increased organizational commitment among Chinese employees. Sadaf et al. (2022) affirmed that POS, organizational value systems, and job satisfaction were strong predictors of organizational commitment.

The recent studies have enlightened on the mediating variables where POS has an influence on organizational commitment. Akkaca (2023) has established job satisfaction as a crucial partial mediator between POS-OC relationship among academic staff members, suggesting that POS influences commitment through satisfaction processes. Silva et al. (2022) demonstrated that POS and affective organizational commitment had mediating variables of job involvement and job satisfaction. Kurniawan (2024) determined that POS positively influenced organizational commitment among employees who felt happy at work as an intervening variable, which, in its turn, is applicable to the project management situation, in particular, as it suggests that the beliefs about support could lead to commitment even in a high-energy work environment.

Research in Indonesia has repeatedly shown that there are strong positive relationships between POS and organizational or affective commitment in various industries (Cahaya and Rahyuda, 2019; Febriantoro, 2018; Nurfayani and Wibawa, 2022; Astuty and Udin, 2020; Renggi and Yudhistira, 2024; Diana & Satrya, 2024). These results can be related to the Organizational Support Theory that states that employees who feel organizational support form emotional relationships with their organizations using socioemotional processes (Eisenberger et al., 1986; Rhoades and Eisenberger, 2002).

Evidence from the IT Consulting Sector

In IT consultancy industry in particular, the study has started to focus on the dynamics of POS and commitment. In a survey of IT consultancy professionals in Spain, Suárez-Albanchez et al. (2022) discovered that the organizational commitment was an effective protective factor against turnover intentions in an industry with turnover rates of about 15%. Their results showed that the affective and normative commitment to the firm rose when the consultants felt that there was more organizational support and improved working conditions, which resulted in a tremendous drop in their intention to leave.

With these findings, Huang et al. (2021) have been able to establish the connection between the leader-member exchange and turnover intention mediated by POS, which serves as an additional factor to the idea of the supportive leadership being mediated by the organizational level of care. The concept of internal listening and support was proven to have a substantial impact on the engagement and commitment of remote workers by Qin (2024), and it can be directly applied to deployed consultants. Weng et al. (2023) observed that POS and work engagement were important in the sustainability of talents in high-demand jobs in the consultancy profession especially in combination with work-life factors.

Such sector-specific results are supported by more general evidence. Zhu et al. (2022) discovered that there was a significant negative correlation between POS and turnover intention irrespective of organizational setting, which supports the argument that improving support perceptions is a universal strategy to decrease staff turnover. Wahyuni (2021) has shown that there was a negative correlation between organizational

commitment and loneliness at work with a high level of POS being essential in reducing turnover intention by establishing a psychological bond to the organization- a fact that is especially applicable to project managers in the staff augmentation setting where they might feel out of place with the home organization.

Contradictory and Qualifying Evidence

Although supportive evidence is overwhelmingly common, there is a growing body of research, which has inconsistent results that should be subject to critical evaluation. These studies indicate that the POS-OC relationship might not be as simple as initially conceptualized, and contextual and methodological factors have an impact on the strength and direction of the relationship.

Gustyana et al. (2018) conducted research in a drinking water company in Bandung, Indonesia, and found that POS had no significant effect on affective commitment, a finding directly contrary to the theoretical expectations of Organizational Support Theory. The study used partial correlation analysis with 85 participants and showed that, when controlling for other variables, the hypothesized relationship between support perceptions and emotional attachment did not materialize. Aliddin et al. (2024) examined employees at the Regional Secretariat Office of Southeast Sulawesi Province and similarly found that POS did not significantly influence organizational commitment despite social support having a significant impact. Their structural equation modeling analysis with 84 employees showed that organizational commitment did not mediate the relationship between POS and employee performance.

The mediating role of organizational commitment has also been questioned. Suharto and Suprpto (2023) studied civil servants in the Directorate General of Treasury in Indonesia and found that while POS had a direct, positive, and significant effect on organizational commitment, employee engagement, and employee performance, organizational commitment did not directly affect employee performance and was not a significant mediator. Franselina et al. (2026) studied employees at the Yogyakarta Central Post Office and showed that while POS and organizational commitment were positively related, bootstrapping results indicated that organizational commitment did not significantly mediate the relationship between POS and either employee engagement or turnover intention. Additional qualifying evidence from Lasamahu and Huwae (2022) indicated no significant relationship between POS and psychological well-being, suggesting boundary conditions for the effectiveness of organizational support interventions.

The Boundary Spanning Perspective

Another aspect of the POS-OC relationship is the scope of the project manager position, which is that of a boundary-spanning role. According to the theory of the boundary spanning, employees working at the border of the home organization and external entities are exposed to special stressors that need special organizational practices (Aldrich and Herker, 1977; Marchington, et al., 2005). Marrone et al. (2021) explored supportive coaching behaviors in relation to boundary-spanning employees and emphasized the significance of organizational support mechanisms in relation to organizational boundary-crossing employees.

Verweij et al. (2023) examined the concept of boundary spanning in the context of a public-private collaboration and discovered that top management support and co-worker support played significant roles in determining the role stress and activity of the boundary spanners, although their study showed that little research existed on organizational support of a boundary-spanning role. These roles are further complicated in outsourced information systems development projects when the managers need to traverse external client-vendor boundaries, and internal stakeholder groups. Gantman and Fedorowicz (2011) maintained that quality and degree of cross-boundary communication is a direct determinant to the results of projects and thus pointed out that mature organizational practice is required to facilitate the intensive communication requirements of project managers. In a meta-analysis of employee boundary-spanner behavior, Li et al. (2022) reported that the organizational commitment was enhanced by the use of the boundary-spanning behavior and implied that the correlation between organizational support and the commitment of the boundary-spanner needs further research in various professional settings.

Synthesis of the Evidence

The combination of empirical evidence offered a multifaceted vision of the POS-OC relationship. Although most of the studies indicated a positive connection, the opposite results of Gustyana et al. (2018), Aliddin et al. (2024), Suharto and Suprpto (2023), and Franselina et al. (2026) suggested that this association was not universal. These discrepancies can be attributed to a number of factors.

Firstly, the POS-OC relationship can be moderated by contextual differences in organizational settings. The insignificant results in non-significant findings in the Indonesian public sector organizations indicated that sector specific factors including bureaucratic structures, motivation of the public sector, or job security might be undermining the influence of POS on commitment. This was particularly true to the current study where the target population is project managers in a privately owned IT consulting firm where the work was boundary-spanning, which complicated the work even more.

Secondly, the mediating processes assumed by Organizational Support Theory might be more complicated than before. The observation that organizational commitment was not significantly mediating the POS-performance relationship in some studies (Suharto and Suprpto, 2023; Franselina et al., 2026) hinted at the possibility that other mediators (e.g., job satisfaction, psychological empowerment, or leader-member exchange) could be more relevant in terms of the relationship of support perceptions to organizational outcomes.

Third, conflicting findings may be caused by methodological differences. The results of studies that utilize various methods of analysis (partial correlation vs. structural equation modeling), varying sample features (private vs. public sector, various industries), etc. could give inconsistent results as a result of differences in measurement accuracy, sample heterogeneity, and statistical power.

Meta-Analytic Evidence on POS and Organizational Outcomes

The aggregate of meta-analytic studies has given strong large-scale support of the association between POS and various organizational outcomes such as organizational

commitment. These integrative reviews have combined the results of hundreds of primary studies and provide high confidence in generalizability of POS effects.

The seminal meta-analysis by Rhoades and Eisenberger (2002) was the first attempt to summarize POS research comprehensively. Their review showed that the employees who felt that the organization was more supportive of them always reported higher affective commitment, increased overall organizational commitment, higher job satisfaction and reduced turnover intentions in a large diversity of sectors and populations. This meta-analysis laid the groundwork of Organizational Support Theory and provided the basis on which future studies have been compared.

Riggle et al. (2009) further developed these results by incorporating 20 years of cumulative studies into a meta-analysis that determined that POS had a moderate to strong association with organizational commitment and job satisfaction, and a strong and negative association with turnover intentions. Their results have justified the practical significance of POS as a driver of motivation to retain employee welfare with effect sizes that were stable regardless of methodological and contextual differences.

The latest meta-analytic review of the Organizational Support Theory was done by Kurtessis et al. (2017). Their results confirmed the positive correlation between POS and affective commitment, and between POS and organizational identification. They also explained the antecedent routes to POS, which proved the main driving forces to be fairness perceptions, supervisor support, and human resource practices.

Eisenberger et al. (2020) provided a temporal and cross-cultural view most recently. Their review revealed that the beneficial impact on employee attitudes and

behavior had lasted over the past thirty years and that, notably, and more significantly, these benefits were more pronounced in Eastern, collectivist societies than in Western, individualist societies. The implication of this finding to the Philippine context is clear, and it can be argued that organizational support could be a highly effective impact on employee commitment in cultures that endorse relational reciprocity and collective welfare.

Li et al. (2022) performed a meta-analysis in the domain of boundary-spanning behavior and concluded that organizational commitment was facilitated by boundary-spanning behavior but suggested that the reciprocal relation between organizational support and the commitment of the boundary-spanner be explored further in various work settings. Zhu et al. (2022) also discovered a strong negative meta-analytic correlation between POS and turnover intention, which is further evidence that perceptions are a universally applicable mechanism to minimize the rates of attrition irrespective of the organizational environment.

Turnover and Attrition in IT Consulting and BPO Sectors

The opening of this paper has mentioned the estimated 22.6% turnover rate in the Philippine consulting sector (Aon, 2025), and a deeper analysis of the literature on turnover is needed to put the value of POS as a retention tool in perspective. Historically, there has been a high rate of attrition within the IT consulting and BPO sector and this is a result of a combination of structural, economic, and psychosocial forces.

It has been reported that average turnover rates in the Asian IT consulting and BPO industries have been attributed to competitive compensation, mobility in career,

globalization of technical skills, and perception of lack of organizational support (Presbitero et al., 2016). The Philippine BPO context revealed that organizational commitment, especially affective commitment, was a very good predictor of turnover intention, with the likelihood of employees who reported emotional attachment to their organization being considerably less (Hechanova 2013). These results are consistent with the general turnover literature that has found organizational commitment to be one of the most consistent proximal antecedents of voluntary turnover (Griffeth et al., 2000; Hom et al., 2017).

POS has been specifically considered in terms of attenuating turnover in project-based context. In their research, Treuren and Fein (2018) have proven that POS was a strong negative predictor of turnover intention in the project-based workplaces, which means that organizational support was a buffer against voluntary turnover despite the high mobility of a certain industry. Joseph et al. (2007) studied the turnover in IT professionals in particular and discovered that a combination of job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and perceived organizational support explicated much variation in turnover intentions, with POS becoming a significant predictor in the retention equation. Ahuja et al. (2007) examined the IT professionals and established that low organizational commitment and job dissatisfaction were some of the most salient antecedents of turnover intentions in the technology industry.

However, the turnover literature has also expressed that POS is not sufficient to explain the dynamics of attrition. The external pull factors (high compensation rates in other organizations, IT project management skills are needed around the globe, and career growth in multinational corporations) are not dependent on the perceptions of

internal support (Griffeth et al., 2000; Hom et al., 2017). This difference was critical to the interpretation of the results of the current study: although POS accounted for 46.1% of the variance in the overall organizational commitment, the rest of the unexplainable variance might be explained by these external market forces and structural factors that cannot be explained by organizational support alone.

The issue of attrition is also further complicated in the Philippine context by the fact that the country is located in the global outsourcing market. The second-largest BPO destination in the world is the Philippines (Tholons, 2019), and the labor market competition that follows generates the continuous upward pressure on the employee's mobility. In the case of IT consulting firms such as 77GSI where the project managers are deployed to the client sites, the dual-allegiance dynamic further complicates the situation: the deployed employees might feel stronger identification with the client organization than with the home firm (Vora & Kostova, 2007), undermining the organizational support-commitment relationship and complicating the retention strategies.

POS and Practical HR Interventions for Retention

There is an increasing body of literature that has linked POS to certain HR interventions designed to further retention. This research area is especially pertinent to IT consulting companies with high turnover rates as it will help to convert the theoretical significance of POS into practical organization-level actions.

Shanock et al. (2019) hypothesized that target practices such as formal onboarding programs, training supervisor support, clear communication and organizational changes, and recognition systems based on organizational values could

optimize POS. Their framework focused on the fact that POS is not a rigid employee perception, but a flexible organizational resource, which can be intentionally developed through systematic human resource interventions.

Allen et al. (2003) presented background evidence that socialization practices, especially those that conveyed organizational care and inclusion, were good predictors of POS that in turn were good predictors of affective commitment and low turnover. Their study laid the theoretical framework of the early organizational practices, via POS, to the long-term commitment outcome, indicating that the onboarding period is a prime phase in creating support perceptions in the newly deployed employees.

In the context of IT consulting in the case relevant to the current study, Suárez-Albanchez et al. (2022) showed that the consultants with higher organizational support perceptions had much lower turnover intentions. They urged consultancy firms to make investments in relation support process instead of only financial retention programs. Their results were that relationship-based interventions including frequent check-ins with deployed consultants, mentoring programs, and available pathways of escalation could prove to be more efficient in the development of commitment than the transactional ones.

Kossek et al. (2011) also added to this body of literature by showing that family-supportive supervisor practices and work-life balance policies promoted POS and decreased turnover intentions especially in employees in high-demand professional jobs. To project managers who work within the constraints of client-site deployment and project timelines, such work-life support systems can be a viable lever to improving the support perceptions that lead to commitment.

The overall findings were consistent with the practical recommendation, which suggested that the application of POS-motivated HR interventions, such as structured check-ins of deployed consultants, the acknowledgment of the project milestones, proactive support of escalation, and training of supervisors in supportive behaviors, could be implemented as concrete retention leverages within IT consulting firms with high turnover rates. In the case of 77GSI, these lessons indicated that a translation of POS as a theoretical concept to a managed organizational activity may be delivered in real improvements in project manager retention.

Research Gap and the Present Study

Although there had been a lot of literature on POS and organizational commitment, there were several gaps that the current study aimed to fill. Rhoades and Eisenberger (2002), in their seminal meta-analysis, openly put forward the necessity to diversify POS research into other occupations and organizational contexts other than the traditional sectors that are frequently examined. Likewise, Kurtessis et al. (2017) found a knowledge gap in the literature on particular industry sectors and professional groups, as most POS investigations have been done in conventional organizational settings, and the use of POS in project-based, boundary-spanning work settings of consulting firms is under-investigated.

In the context of project management specifically, Meyer et al. (1993) distinguished between organizational commitment and professional commitment, noting that these forms of commitment might have different antecedents and consequences among professional workers. However, they acknowledged that empirical research examining

these differences among project workers remained limited. Turner and Müller (2003) further observed that project commitment is conceptually distinct from organizational commitment, yet little research had explored the role of organizational-level factors such as POS in shaping organizational commitment among project managers specifically. Most project management research has emphasized project-level commitment or top management support for projects rather than the global POS construct as defined in Organizational Support Theory.

The fact that project-oriented sectors have had empirical evidence to support this gap also supports the existence of this gap. In a study of a construction company, Sherwani (2019) discovered that POS was a much better predictor of organizational commitment than general employee behavior, indicating that support was particularly relevant in predicting attachment in project-intensive industries. Araújo and Pedron (2017) discovered a gap in the existing research on competencies of project managers and their association with commitment, whereby technical competencies require fulfillment, yet it is the psychological attachment to the company that leads to the successful delivery in the long-term. In their study of organizational and professional commitment in project workers, Pedron et al. (2010) determined that there were strong correlations between these two types of commitment, but they concluded that further research was necessary to comprehend the peculiarities of commitment of project workers. They particularly requested research on the extent to which organizational support practices might encourage organizational and professional commitment among this group of the workforce.

Recent studies in IT consultancy have further highlighted the need for dedicated research. Suárez-Albanchez et al. (2022) explicitly noted the lack of research studying organizational commitment in the IT consulting sector despite its high turnover rates and strategic importance. The boundary-spanning nature of the project manager role compounds this gap: Verweij et al. (2023) found that top management and co-worker support significantly influenced boundary spanners' role stress and activities but observed that research on organizational support for boundary-spanning roles remained limited. Li et al. (2022) similarly recommended that the relationship between organizational support and boundary-spanner commitment be further investigated in diverse professional contexts.

Pattnaik et al. (2020) added a nuanced dimension by discovering that the positive link between POS and organizational commitment was significantly strengthened when employees experienced high person-organization fit. This suggested that for project managers at 77GSI, organizational support might be most effective when congruent with the professional values and mission of the firm.

The current paper has answered these identified gaps by looking at the predictive relationship between POS and OC in project managers at 77GSI where the work arrangements are characterized by boundary-spanning roles, client-site deployment, and project-based work arrangements. By examining the hypothesis that POS was a significant predictor of organizational commitment and its three dimensions in this particular setting, the study added to the existing body of empirical evidence that either supported or disproved the applicability of the Organizational Support Theory to the modern IT consulting setting. The results were especially useful considering the mixed

evidence examined above, to inform the degree to which the POS-OC relationship was true among employees who went through dual loyalties to the home organization and to their client organizations where they were posted.

CHAPTER III: METHODS AND PROCEDURES

Research Design

This research utilized a causal research design that has a quantitative ex post facto research tradition. As defined by Cohen et al. (2018, pp. 420-421), causal research, which differs from causal-comparative research, is concerned with finding antecedents to a current condition by looking for the directional relationship between variables that are represented as $X \rightarrow O$, where X is the independent variable and O is the dependent variable. While true experimental, causal research involves manipulation of variables and random assignment, the ex post facto causal design used in this study investigates naturally occurring phenomena where the independent variable (POS) has already occurred and cannot be manipulated by the researcher (Cohen et al., 2018).

The main objective of this causal inquiry was to establish whether Perceived Organizational Support (X) is used as an antecedent to Organizational Commitment (O) in the case of project managers at 77GSI. This way, cause-and-effect relations can be studied in a natural organizational context where experimentation is neither possible nor ethical. In line with the standards of the American Psychological Association (2020) for quantitative research, the variables were measured in their natural state unaltered by systematic manipulation.

As this research was based on cross-sectional, self-administered survey data, the researcher considered the issue of common method bias (Podsakoff et al., 2003). To combat this, psychological separators were included in the survey instrument between

measurement of POS and OC sections. The separators by section were the cognitive breaks for the participant, in order to stimulate the respondents to focus on the feeling of commitment rather than perceptions of organizational support, reducing the risk of artificial correlation between constructs.

As outlined by Jackson (2011), the study made use of Likert scales which translate subjective perceptions into quantifiable data, which can be analyzed using parametric statistics. Simple linear regression analysis was used to determine the impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable. There were four separate regression models which were tested in this study, these are: (a) POS predicting overall OC, (b) POS predicting affective commitment, (c) POS predicting continuance commitment, and (d) POS predicting normative commitment. This analytical strategy estimated the proportion of variance explained (R^2) by POS for each outcome of commitment.

Findings were reported in accordance with American Psychological Association (2020) standards for quantitative research (JARS-Quant), including sample size, F-values with degrees of freedom, exact p values, confidence intervals and effect size (R^2 and b) to show the magnitude of the causal relationship between POS and OC.

Research Locale

Project managers working for 77GSI were the target respondents for the study. The researcher's company is with the 77GSI headquarters at 27th Floor, The Orient Square Building, F. Ortigas Jr. Road (formerly Emerald Avenue), Ortigas Center, Pasig City, Metro Manila, Philippines 1605. This setting was appropriate because project managers work within a project-based environment, where the regular occurrence of

schedule pressure, scope changes, stakeholder demands and accountability for delivery outcomes are regular.

The population for the study were project managers deployed to client sites under staff augmentation or consulting arrangements from this central headquarters. That work setup put project managers at the intersection of the home organization (77GSI at Orient Square) and the client environment, which made perceptions of organizational support especially relevant. Locating the study in 77GSI's Philippine operations in this particular location is meant to ensure that the findings are interpreted in the organizational and cultural context of a major IT consulting hub in Ortigas Center, rather than generalized to other countries or industries without further evidence.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sampling method used in this study was census (total population sampling) and not probability sampling. Since the target population of Project Managers at 77GSI was small, limited and accessible to the full extent because of the Community of Practice PM Group at the company, all members eligible to take part in it were invited to participate and no statistical sampling frame was drawn. Under these circumstances, a census is suitable since it would remove the error of sampling, maximize statistical power and the result would be based on the entire population of interest and not an inferential estimate based on a sub-population (Cohen et al., 2018; Sevilla et al., 1992).

The total population of Project Managers at 77GSI was $N = 76$. The researcher, who met the inclusion criteria, excluded himself from participation to avoid researcher bias, reducing the eligible population to $N = 75$. Participants satisfied the following inclusion

criteria: (a) currently employed by 77GSI, (b) held the official title of Project Manager, and (c) were currently deployed to a client engagement at the time of data collection.

All eligible 75 Project Managers were contacted, and their 100% response rate was obtained. Since the study was an entire enumeration of the target population, there was no sample size computation or inferential sampling formula used; the statistical tests were done on the entire census of eligible Project Managers.

In line with the causal research design, which aims at examining the direct POS-OC relationship, demographic factors (age, gender, civil status, and tenure) were not measured because theoretically, they could not be considered covariates in the causal model under study (Cohen et al., 2018).

Research Instrument

This study made use of a structured online survey questionnaire that is made up of two widely validated instruments. To assess Perceived Organizational Support (POS), the current study included the 8-item short version of the Survey of Perceived Organizational Support (SPOS) written by Eisenberger, Huntington, Hutchison, and Sowa (1986). This shorter version was chosen as it reduced respondent fatigue while retaining a unidimensional structure that accurately reflects the global beliefs of the employees on how much the organization values their contributions and well-being. The 8 items are scored using a 7-point Likert-type scale from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 7 (Strongly Agree). In the research of Hellman et al. (2006) and Worley et al. (2009) they used the 8-item version and have found excellent internal consistency, with values of Cronbach Alpha ranging from .90 to .95.

Table 1

Survey of Perceived Organizational Support (SPOS)

Item #	Item Content
1	The organization values my contribution to its well-being.
2	If the organization could hire someone to replace me at a lower salary, it would do so. (R)
3	The organization fails to appreciate any extra effort from me. (R)
4	The organization strongly considers my goals and values.
5	The organization would ignore any complaint from me. (R)
6	The organization disregards my best interests when it makes decisions that affect me. (R)
7	Help is available from the organization when I have a problem.
8	The organization really cares about my well-being.

Note. (R) indicates a reverse-scored item. Responses are recorded on a 7-point Likert scale from 1 (*Strongly Disagree*) to 7 (*Strongly Agree*). From "Perceived Organizational Support," by R. Eisenberger, R. Huntington, S. Hutchison, and D. Sowa, 1986, *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 71(3), p. 501 (<https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.71.3.500>). Copyright 1986 by the American Psychological Association.

To assess Organizational Commitment (OC), the research used the 18-item revised Three-Component Model (TCM) Employee Commitment Survey developed by Meyer, Allen, and Smith (1993). This instrument was chosen because it is the most dominant theoretical framework for understanding the multidimensional nature of organizational commitment distinguishing its affective (6 items), continuance (6 items) and normative (6 items) dimensions. Similar to SPOS, the TCM has a 7-point Likert-type scale rating from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 7 (Strongly Agree). In the psychometric evaluations conducted by Meyer et al. (1993), they have determined strong reliability for its subscales,

with Cronbach's alpha values of .85 for affective commitment, .79 for continuance commitment, and .73 for normative commitment (Meyer et al., 1993).

Table 2

Three-Component Model (TCM)

Component/Item	Item Content
Affective 1	I would be very happy to spend the rest of my career with this organization.
Affective 2	I really feel as if this organization's problems are my own.
Affective 3 (R)	I do not feel a strong sense of "belonging" to my organization.
Affective 4 (R)	I do not feel "emotionally attached" to this organization.
Affective 5 (R)	I do not feel like "part of the family" at my organization.
Affective 6	This organization has a great deal of personal meaning for me.
Continuance 1	Right now, staying with my organization is a matter of necessity as much as desire.
Continuance 2	It would be very hard for me to leave my organization right now, even if I wanted to.
Continuance 3	Too much of my life would be disrupted if I decided I wanted to leave my organization now.
Continuance 4	I feel that I have too few options to consider leaving this organization.
Continuance 5	If I had not already put so much of myself into this organization, I might consider working elsewhere.
Continuance 6	One of the few negative consequences of leaving this organization would be the scarcity of available alternatives.
Normative 1 (R)	I do not feel any obligation to remain with my current employer.
Normative 2	Even if it were to my advantage, I do not feel it would be right to leave my organization now.
Normative 3	I would feel guilty if I left my organization now.
Normative 4	This organization deserves my loyalty.
Normative 5	I would not leave my organization right now because I have a sense of obligation to the people in it.
Normative 6	I owe a great deal to this organization.

Note. Responses are measured using a 7-Point Likert Scale between 1 (*Strongly Disagree*) and 7 (*Strongly Agree*). Reprinted from "Commitment to Organizations and Occupations: Extension and Test of a Three-Component Conceptualization," by J. P. Meyer, N. J. Allen, and C. A. Smith, 1993, *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 78(4), p. 539, <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.78.4.538> Copyright 1993 American Psychological Association. Reprinted with permission.

In order to make sure that the research instruments were reliable, this research work has adopted the generally accepted psychometric threshold recommended by Nunnally (1978). In the early stage of research and for most types of behavioral measures, a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of .70 or greater is considered a sufficient measure of internal consistency.

Data Gathering Procedures

Data collection was conducted in a six-phase procedure:

Phase 1: Ethics Clearance and Authorization. Prior to collection of data, written permission was obtained from the management of the 77GSI to have the study conducted. At the same time, the research protocol was submitted to the San Beda College Alabang Research Ethics Committee (REC) for review. Data collection started after receiving formal clearance on the ethics.

This manuscript was prepared using writing tools assisted by AI or generative writing technologies, which are ethical writing aids as per the framework of ethics proposed by Cheng et al. (2025). They were only used in the tasks that belong to Tier 1

(ethically acceptable: grammar and readability) and Tier 2 (ethically contingent: summarizing researcher-generated content, enhancing clarity, and organizing reference material) of the Cheng et al. (2025) framework. The AI tools were not employed to create primary content, study data analysis, literature search, and formulation of new ideas, and reference development at any stage. Every idea, argument, interpretation and conclusion in this manuscript is entirely a product of the researcher.

A total of three AI tools were applied at different stages of preparing the manuscript. Google NotebookLM (Google LLC) was an online document storage and reference system wherein uploaded PDFs of the references and statistical material related to the research were stored and could be accessed and reviewed with ease as the writing process continued. The legibility and paragraph flow of researcher-written text were enhanced with Grammarly (Grammarly Inc.); sample revisions can be found in Appendix K. Claude (Anthropic) was used to generate structured statistical benchmark reference cards, which consolidated authoritative statistical thresholds of researcher-identified sources - such as Cohen (1988), George and Mallery (2003), Evans (1996), Field (2018), and Nunally (1978). An explanation of each tool, the particular purposes and contexts of their application are given in Appendix K. Turnitin was used to check originality and similarity of the manuscript, each individual chapter (Chapters 1 through 5) of the paper and the entire manuscript were sent separately to the thesis professor to be scanned by the institute before submission.

Phase 2: Licensing of the selected Research Instruments. Permission to use the standardized instruments was obtained for TCM. SPOS (Eisenberger et al., 1986) was confirmed for free use for academic purposes with the proper attribution, a courtesy letter

was sent informing the institution for its use. The TCM Employee Commitment Survey (Meyer & Allen, 1997) was obtained under an Academic License from Western University, Canada, allowing for its use for this thesis research.

Phase 3: Participant Notification and Informed Consent. Notice was distributed to all Project Managers ($N = 75$) via the official communication channel of the company detailing both the purpose of the study and that it was voluntary and confidential. The online survey link (Google Forms) had an electronic informed consent form, in which participants would be asked to confirm that they understood the objectives of the study, their rights to withdraw, and data protection measures before accessing the questionnaire.

Phase 4: Monitoring and Rolling Out the Survey. The survey was conducted online over a 3-week period, from March 2, 2026 to March 22, 2026. The questionnaire was designed in three different parts (consent form, SPOS, TCM) with psychological separators through sectioned surveys separating the variables to pages in the Google Forms to minimize common method bias. Weekly reminder group message and direct message were sent to non-respondents at reasonable intervals in order to encourage participation without coercion.

Phase 5: Data Verification and Storing. Upon closing the survey, responses were downloaded and checked for completeness. Completed submissions were used for the analysis; incomplete submissions were excluded from the analysis. Data were stored in password protected files only accessible to the researcher and back up to the cloud was encrypted. No personally identifiable information was collected, which meant anonymity. Prior to data collection, the researcher informed the PMO Manager and Client Delivery

Manager – the decision makers who approved to conduct the study – that a token of appreciation will be extended to them in response to their permission to proceed with the study. Following the closure of data collection, the researcher provided the token as announced. No tokens, incentives, or compensation of any kind were offered to participating project managers, whose participation remained voluntary and anonymous throughout.

Phase 6: Data Retention Plan. In accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 and institutional requirements, raw data are scheduled to be permanently deleted from all devices and cloud storage after one-year post-defense and stored in secure storage to allow retention of the data for one year.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Data analysis was done using JAMOVI software (version 2.6.44; R Core Team, 2024). The statistical procedures were aligned with the research objective as follows.

To begin with, descriptive statistics such as means and standard deviations of Perceived Organizational Support and the three dimensions of Organizational Commitment: affective, continuance, and normative, were calculated. Mean scores were interpreted using a seven-level verbal interpretation scale, and the basic principle underlying the use of Likert scales as interval data to analyze statistical data was followed (Likert, 1932). In line with the approach of descriptive research design (Salkind, 2010), the research used an equal interval formula to the 7-point Likert scale instruments. The interval width was computed as, which is a common practice when creating classification

ranges in Likert based surveys (Pimentel, 2010). These computations led to the ranges of classification in Table 3.

Table 3

Mean Score Range and Verbal Interpretation for a 7-Point Likert Scale

Mean Range	Scale Anchor	Verbal Interpretation
1.00 – 1.85	Strongly Disagree	Very Low
1.86 – 2.71	Moderately Disagree	Low
2.72 – 3.57	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Low
3.58 – 4.43	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Moderate
4.44 – 5.29	Slightly Agree	Slightly High
5.30 – 6.14	Moderately Agree	High
6.15 – 7.00	Strongly Agree	Very High

Note. Interval width = $(7 - 1) / 7 = 0.857$. Reverse-scored items were recorded prior to computing means so that higher values uniformly indicate higher levels of the construct.

Before reverse-coding, the verbal interpretation of the raw scores on these items is inverted: high agreement with a negatively worded statement reflects low score, and vice versa. Table 4 shows the verbal interpretation that applies to the raw (pre-recoded) scores of the reverse-keyed items.

Table 4

Verbal Interpretation for Reverse-Keyed 7-Point Likert Scale Items

Mean Range	Scale Anchor	Interpretation of Raw Score (Pre-Recoding)
1.00 – 1.85	Strongly Disagree	Very High
1.86 – 2.71	Moderately Disagree	High
2.72 – 3.57	Slightly Disagree	Slightly High
3.58 – 4.43	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Moderate
4.44 – 5.29	Slightly Agree	Slightly Low
5.30 – 6.14	Moderately Agree	Low
6.15 – 7.00	Strongly Agree	Very Low

Note. Interval width = $(7 - 1) / 7 = 0.857$. The table indicates the reverse-scored items pre-recoding, which is opposite of the verbal interpretation shown in Table 3.

Second, the assumptions of linearity, normal residuals, and homoscedasticity were evaluated with the help of residual scatterplots, normal Q-Q plots, and Shapiro-Wilk test before the regression analysis was conducted. All the assumptions were met, which shows the validity of the regression models as the detailed diagnostic results are provided in Appendix J.

Third, to find out whether Perceived Organizational Support (X) significantly predicts Organizational Commitment (O), simple linear regression analysis was taken as the primary inferential test, which is in agreement with the causal research design by Cohen et al. (2018). Four different regression models were introduced: (a) POS predicting overall OC, (b) POS predicting affective commitment, (c) POS predicting continuance commitment, and (d) POS predicting normative commitment, The coefficients of determination (R^2) were reported to indicate the proportion of the variance explained by

each regression model, as well as the unstandardized regression coefficient (b), standard error (SE) The interpretation of the effect sizes was based on the benchmarks of R^2 provided by Cohen (1988): small = .02, medium = .13, and large = .26. Results were presented following the APA 7th edition requirements (American Psychological Association, 2020).

CHAPTER IV:

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter presents the results of the statistical analyses conducted to investigate the predictive relationship between Perceived Organizational Support (POS) and Organizational Commitment (OC) among Project Managers at 77GSI. Data were collected from 75 respondents using two validated instruments: the 8-item Survey of Perceived Organizational Support (SPOS) and the 18-item Three-Component Model (TCM) Employee Commitment Survey. The analytic approach comprised descriptive statistics, item-level analysis of both instruments, assessment of regression assumptions, and four simple linear regression models testing the study hypotheses (H_{01} – H_{04}). All mean interpretations in this chapter follow the verbal interpretation scale presented in Chapter 3 (Table 3).

Descriptive Statistics

Table 5 presents the descriptive statistics for the study variables, including the mean, standard deviation, and verbal interpretation for Perceived Organizational Support (POS), the three dimensions of Organizational Commitment (OC)—Affective, Continuance, and Normative—and Organizational Commitment as a whole.

Table 5

Descriptive Statistics for Study Variables (N = 75)

Variable	M	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Perceived Organizational Support	5.26	1.012	Slightly High
Affective Commitment	4.72	0.987	Slightly High
Continuance Commitment	4.85	1.285	Slightly High
Normative Commitment	5.02	1.251	Slightly High
Overall Organizational Commitment	4.87	0.892	Slightly High

Note. All variables measured on a 7-point Likert scale (1=Strongly Disagree to 7=Strongly Agree). M=Mean, SD=Standard Deviation, Min=Minimum, Max=Maximum.

The mean score for Perceived Organizational Support (POS) was 5.26 ($SD = 1.012$). According to the verbal interpretation scale in Table 3 (Chapter 3), this means falls within the 4.44 to 5.29 range, categorized as "Slightly High." This indicates that project managers at 77GSI perceive a slightly high degree of organizational support from their home firm. Among the three dimensions of commitment, Normative Commitment yielded the highest mean ($M = 5.02$, $SD = 1.251$), followed by Continuance Commitment ($M = 4.85$, $SD = 1.285$) and Affective Commitment ($M = 4.72$, $SD = 0.987$). All three dimensions, as well as the Overall Organizational Commitment mean ($M = 4.87$, $SD = 0.892$), fell within the "Slightly High" band. The finding that Normative Commitment ranked higher than Affective Commitment presents a distinct pattern compared to typical Western Three-Component Model (TCM) research. This result aligns with the collectivist orientation of the Philippine workplace, where cultural values such as utang na loob (debt of gratitude) and pakikisama (smooth interpersonal relations) foster a culturally enforced sense of obligation toward the organization (Hofstede, 2001; Jocano, 1997). The Overall OC ($M = 4.87$, $SD = 0.892$) displayed a Slightly High level of commitment and had the lowest SD of any study variable. This SD of the overall score or the mean is more consistent than the separate

parts. Substantively, the average of 4.87 was above the middle of the Slightly High band (4.44 - 5.29) but was contained at the 5.00 level by the relatively restraining Affective Commitment dimension. The resulting profile obligation-led, having a modest emotional attachment in the same Slightly High band and cost-based attachment was structurally consistent with a Filipino, boundary-spanning consulting workforce.

Item-Level Descriptive Statistics

Survey of Perceived Organizational Support (SPOS)

Table 6 presents item-level means and standard deviations for the SPOS after reverse-scoring of the four negatively worded items (Items 2, 3, 5, and 6), so that higher values uniformly indicate greater perceived organizational support.

Table 6

Item-Level Descriptive Statistics for SPOS Items (N = 75)

Item	Item Content	M	SD
1	The organization values my contribution to its well-being.	5.55	1.25
2	If the organization could hire someone to replace me at a lower salary, it would do so. (R)	4.47	1.77
3	The organization fails to appreciate any extra effort from me. (R)	5.11	1.34
4	The organization strongly considers my goals and values.	5.17	1.32
5	The organization would ignore any complaint from me. (R)	5.35	1.27
6	The organization disregards my best interests when it makes decisions that affect me. (R)	5.08	1.52
7	Help is available from the organization when I have a problem.	5.83	1.04
8	The organization really cares about my well-being.	5.56	1.11

Note. (R) = reverse-keyed item, corrected prior to computing means. All items rated on a 7-point Likert scale.

At the item level, the highest-rated SPOS indicator was “Help is available from the organization when I have a problem” (Item 7; $M = 5.83$, $SD = 1.04$, High), followed by “*The organization really cares about my well-being*” (Item 8; $M = 5.56$, $SD = 1.11$, High) and “*The organization values my contribution to its well-being*” (Item 1; $M = 5.55$, $SD = 1.25$, High). The lowest-rated item was the reverse-keyed “*If the organization could hire someone to replace me at a lower salary, it would do so*” (Item 2; $M = 4.47$, $SD = 1.77$, Slightly High), which also produced the largest item-level SD in the SPOS, indicating that perceptions of personal replaceability varied substantially across respondents.

Three-Component Model (TCM) – Subscale Item Means

Item-level means and standard deviations on the Affective, Continuance and Normative Commitment subscales are shown in Tables 7, 8, and 9, respectively. The reverse keyed items were corrected before being computed. According to the official TCM Academic Users Guide (Meyer & Allen, 2004), the Revised Commitment Scale has no reverse keyed items; all six CC items are in their original direction.

Table 7

Item-Level Descriptive Statistics for Affective Commitment Items (N = 75)

Item	Item Content	M	SD
AC1	I would be very happy to spend the rest of my career with this organization.	4.79	1.51
AC2	I really feel as if this organization's problems are my own.	4.45	1.39
AC3	I do not feel a strong sense of “belonging” to my organization. (R)	4.73	1.34
AC4	I do not feel “emotionally attached” to this organization. (R)	4.45	1.47
AC5	I do not feel like “part of the family” at my organization. (R)	4.83	1.28
AC6	This organization has a great deal of personal meaning for me.	5.09	1.18

Note. (R) = reverse-keyed item, corrected prior to computing means. Higher values indicate greater affective commitment.

The Affective Commitment had the lowest mean of the three dimensions of commitment ($M = 4.72$, $SD = 0.987$), which is located at the lower end of the Slightly High band in Table 3. This position was in contrast to the trend that is typically reported in Western TCM studies where Affective Commitment is generally the most common dimension. The most probable reason was the structural circumstances of the deployment of the boundary-spanning role: the project managers physically located in the client locations and bound to the parent firm mainly through administrative means had less to do with the symbolic, cultural, and informal social customs that would otherwise develop emotional attachment. This reading was corroborated by item-level data: the lowest-scoring AC items were AC2 "*I really feel as if this organization problems are my own*" ($M = 4.45$, $SD = 1.39$) and the reverse-keyed AC4 "*I do not feel emotionally attached to this organization*" ($M = 4.45$, $SD = 1.47$) - both of which are tapping psychological ownership and emotional attachment which would be the result of sustained organizational exposure. On the other hand, the most rated AC item was AC6 "*This organization has a great deal of personal meaning to me*" ($M = 5.09$, $SD = 1.18$, Slightly High) indicating that project managers still had significant sense of identification with the firm despite the physical distance.

Table 8

Item-Level Descriptive Statistics for Continuance Commitment Items (N = 75)

Item	Item Content	M	SD
CC1	Right now, staying with my organization is a matter of necessity as much as desire.	5.57	1.40
CC2	It would be very hard for me to leave my organization right now, even if I wanted to.	4.97	1.53
CC3	Too much of my life would be disrupted if I decided I wanted to leave my organization now.	4.96	1.76
CC4	I feel that I have too few options to consider leaving this organization.	4.64	1.71
CC5	If I had not already put so much of myself into this organization, I might consider working elsewhere.	4.09	1.61
CC6	One of the few negative consequences of leaving this organization would be the scarcity of available alternatives.	4.88	1.67

Note. The Revised TCM Continuance Commitment Scale contains no reverse-keyed items (Meyer & Allen, 2004). All items scored in original direction. Higher values indicate greater continuance commitment.

Continuance Commitment ($M = 4.85$, $SD = 1.285$) achieved the biggest standard deviation of the five study variables. This dispersion was congruent with the construct: A Continuance Commitment is not mediated by relational and cultural forces that tend to make responses in a group more homogeneous, but rather the individualized computations of costs and benefits (the perceived labor-market alternatives, the accumulated sunk costs, tenure-contingent benefits, and client-specific relational capital). The cost of leaving may have been rated by a project manager who has a tenure of two years into a single deployment much differently than by a senior project manager that had five years of specialized knowledge of clients, and that individual-level difference is translated into the item-level dispersion. The highest rated CC item was CC1 “*Right now,*

staying with my organization is a matter of necessity as much as desire” ($M = 5.57$, $SD = 1.40$, High), which reflected a concrete feeling of calculative lock-in, likely due to the relative scarcity of directly equivalent jobs in the Philippine IT consulting labor market. In comparison, the lowest-rated in the entire 26-item instrument was CC5 “If I had not already put so much of myself into this organization, I might consider working elsewhere” ($M = 4.09$, $SD = 1.61$, Moderate), indicating that some of the respondent project managers did not regard 77GSI as the company that they belong to. They feel like they belong to the clients they serve. They stay with the company because it’s a matter of necessity, but they aren’t putting psychological roots down. There are project managers who think that they are renting their skills to the home-firm, but their career aspiration is with the client.

Table 9

Item-Level Descriptive Statistics for Normative Commitment Items (N = 75)

Item	Item Content	M	SD
NC1	I do not feel any obligation to remain with my current employer. (R)	4.71	1.58
NC2	Even if it were to my advantage, I do not feel it would be right to leave my organization now.	4.91	1.57
NC3	I would feel guilty if I left my organization now.	4.93	1.59
NC4	This organization deserves my loyalty.	5.07	1.66
NC5	I would not leave my organization right now because I have a sense of obligation to the people in it.	5.19	1.39
NC6	I owe a great deal to this organization.	5.32	1.64

Note. (R) = reverse-keyed item, corrected prior to computing means. Higher values indicate greater normative commitment.

Normative Commitment recorded the greatest average of all the three dimensions of commitment ($M = 5.02$, $SD = 1.251$, Slightly High), which is the opposite of the Affective-

dominant trend in Western TCM literature. The high Normative mean was indicative of the culturally specific obligation norms within the Philippine workforce. This interpretation was supported by item-level inspection: highest rated NC items were NC6 “*I owe a great deal to this organization*” ($M = 5.32$, $SD = 1.64$, High) and NC5 “*I would not leave my organization right now because I have a sense of obligation to the people in it*” ($M = 5.19$, $SD = 1.39$, Slightly High). Both items put obligation in a relational and reciprocal sense which are the repayment of received care that we call *utang na loob* (indebtedness) as well as *pakikisama* (smooth interpersonal relations). This dimension with the greatest mean was not the product of policy pressure or a contractual lock-in, but rather of a collectivist outlook where perceived organizational support triggers a moral-debt reaction. The SD of 1.251 was quite large, which suggested the differences between the levels of how strongly *utang na loob* worked among respondents: project managers who personally attributed their career development, stability, or sponsorship to 77GSI scored higher on the obligation scale, and those whose growth was mostly client-driven scored lower.

Across the three dimensions, the item-level pattern converged on a coherent profile. For Affective Commitment, “*This organization has a great deal of personal meaning for me*” (AC6; $M = 5.09$) was rated highest. For Continuance Commitment, “*Right now, staying with my organization is a matter of necessity as much as desire*” (CC1; $M = 5.57$) ranked highest, with “*If I had not already put so much of myself into this organization, I might consider working elsewhere*” (CC5; $M = 4.09$) ranked lowest. For Normative Commitment, “*I owe a great deal to this organization*” (NC6; $M = 5.32$) and “*I would not leave my organization right now because I have a sense of obligation to the people in it*” (NC5; $M = 5.19$) gained the highest endorsements -- a pattern consistent with the Filipino cultural value of *utang na loob* (debt of gratitude).

Assessment of Regression Assumptions

Before interpreting the regression results, the three main assumptions of simple linear regression which include linearity, normality of residuals, and homoscedasticity were evaluated in each of the four regression models. Diagnostic tests were visual inspection of bivariate scatterplots, residuals-versus-fitted-values plot, normal Q-Q plot and Shapiro-Wilk test of normality. The Appendix J gives the detailed results of these assumption checks; all the four models met the assumptions of linearity and homoscedasticity. Three models passed the test of normality of assumption; Normative Commitment model demonstrated a slight violation (Shapiro-Wilk $W = .965$, $p = .037$) which was identified upon visual inspection to be slight and non-significant. Since at a sample size around 75 and beyond, regression is resistant to small normality violations (Field, 2018; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2019), all four models are viewed with confidence.

Simple Linear Regression Analyses

Four simple linear regression analyses were performed to investigate the predictive relationship between POS and each OC outcome as indicated in Table 10. The following paragraph flow was interpreted by stating the results, statistical explanation, connection to the literature, and implications for practice.

Table 10

Summary of Simple Linear Regression Analyses Predicting Organizational Commitment Given Perceived Organizational Support (N = 75)

Dependent Variable	R²	F (df = 1, 73)	b	SE	p	95% CI for b
Overall OC	.461	62.35**	0.598	0.076	< .001	[0.447, 0.749]
Affective Commitment	.424	53.68**	0.634	0.087	< .001	[0.462, 0.807]
Continuance Commitment	.090	7.18*	0.380	0.142	.009	[0.097, 0.662]
Normative Commitment	.399	48.41**	0.780	0.112	< .001	[0.557, 1.004]

Note. OC = Organizational Commitment; *b* = unstandardized regression coefficient; *SE* = standard error. All models: *df* = 1, 73. * *p* < .01. ** *p* < .001.

POS Predicting Overall Organizational Commitment

Simple linear regression showed that Perceived Organizational Support significantly predicted Overall Organizational Commitment, $F(1, 73) = 62.35, p < .001, R^2 = .461$, Adjusted $R^2 = .453$. The unstandardized regression coefficient ($b = 0.598, SE = 0.076, 95\% CI [0.447, 0.749]$) indicated that each one-unit increase in POS corresponded to a 0.598-unit increase in Overall OC. On this basis, the null hypothesis H_01 , that POS does not significantly predict Overall OC among project managers at 77GSI, was rejected.

The POS explained 46.1% of the variation in the Overall OC, which is greater than the large effect size ($R^2 = .26$) established by Cohen (1988). Compared to the descriptive profile, which was reported above, in which both POS ($M = 5.26$, Slightly High) and the Overall OC ($M = 4.87$, Slightly High) were within the 4.445 - 5.29 range of Table 3, the regression coefficient showed that change in POS was a systematic predictor of change

in OC within this range. The narrow 95% confidence interval [0.447, 0.749] did not contain zero value and thus, the predictive estimate was both directionally strong and statistically accurate.

This correlation was of the same magnitude as the Chapter 2 review. Meta-analytic results by Rhoades and Eisenberger (2002) and Kurtessis et al. (2017) revealed a strong and general POS-OC relationship within industries and geographies. In the Philippine contexts, Andrin and Dumale (2023) found that the POS and OC were strongly correlated among the local government workers, and Suárez-Albanchez et al. (2022) discovered that organizational support was a key protective factor against turnover intention in Spanish IT consultancy. The current result also expanded this body of evidence into the neglected group of project managers who are boundary-spanners in the Philippine IT consulting sector, proving that the main postulation of the Organizational Support Theory (Eisenberger et al., 1986) applied to the present context. When viewed through the factors of a Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964; Cropanzano and Mitchell, 2005), the outcome also showed that project managers were involved in a reciprocal exchange: the higher the organizational care went beyond the contractual baselines, the higher the project managers returned the commitment to the firm.

In the case of 77GSI, the results of the study indicate that investment in organizational support practices like recognition programs, readily available escalation channels, and visible career advocacy, could be anticipated to give quantifiable returns in home-firm commitment, despite the physical deployment of project managers in client settings. The high effect size further corroborated the claim that support practices were

not fringe retention levers but core ones: almost half of the difference in commitment could be attributed to the way supported project managers felt at 77GSI.

POS Predicting Affective Commitment

POS significantly predicted Affective Commitment, $F(1, 73) = 53.68, p < .001, R^2 = .424$, Adjusted $R^2 = .416$. The coefficient of regression ($b = 0.634, SE = 0.087, 95\% CI [0.462, 0.807]$) was not standardized, which meant that an increase in POS by a unit resulted in an increase in Affective Commitment by 0.634 units. The null hypothesis H_{02} - that POS does not significantly predict Affective Commitment amongst project managers at 77GSI, was rejected.

The variance in Affective Commitment attributed to Perceived Organizational Support (POS) was 42.4% ($R^2 = .424$), which constitutes a large effect based on Cohen's (1988) standards. Since Affective Commitment ($M = 4.72$, "Slightly High") was at the lower end of the 4.44 – 5.29 range—making it the lowest of the three commitment dimensions—a large effect size suggests that POS is a powerful lever capable of pushing Affective Commitment further up the scale. Furthermore, the narrow 95% confidence interval [0.462, 0.807] did not contain zero, which justifies the accuracy of the estimate.

This finding was in line with Chapter 2 review on Affective Commitment. Silva et al. (2022) reported a direct effect of POS on Affective Commitment in the professional setting, with research in the Indonesian workforce by Astuty and Udin (2020), and Nurfayani and Wibawa (2022) also showing consistent positive correlations. The Organizational Support Theory (Eisenberger et al., 1986; Rhoades and Eisenberger, 2002) hypothesizes that perceived organizational care will meet socioemotional needs of

approval, affiliation, and esteem - generating emotional attachment to the organization. This mechanism was empirically validated in the current finding among the project managers who serve as the boundary spanners in their respective projects and the theoretical pathway is carried over to the Philippine IT consulting context.

In the case of 77GSI leadership, the result showed that support systems that are indicative of a true sense of care as opposed to a transactional or a purely financial one would be the most effective in fostering emotional attachment of the home-firm to the project managers once they have been deployed to the client location. Since Affective Commitment had the least mean among the three dimensions ($M = 4.72$), it was the most headroom dimension to be increased, and the significant predictive value of the POS was an indication that specific support investments would have a significant impact on bridging that gap.

POS Predicting Continuance Commitment

POS significantly predicted Continuance Commitment, $F(1, 73) = 7.18, p = .009, R^2 = .090, \text{Adjusted } R^2 = .077$. The coefficient was not standardized ($b = 0.380, SE = 0.142, 95\% \text{ CI } [0.097, 0.662]$) meaning that every one-unit change in POS was related to a 0.380-unit change in Continuance Commitment. The null hypothesis, H_03 - that POS does not significantly predict Continuance Commitment among project managers at 77GSI, was rejected.

POS explained 9.0% of the variance in Continuance Commitment - a small to medium effect by Cohen's (1988) standards (small = .02, medium = .13). The effect was significantly less relative to those of Overall OC, Affective Commitment, and Normative

Commitment but the result was statistically significant and the 95% CI [0.097, 0.662] was not equal to zero. Placed in the context of the descriptive profile, Continuance commitment ($M = 4.85$, Slightly High) was in the middle of the means of AC and NC and had the highest item-level SD in the research (SD up to 1.76 on CC3). The great diversity of the answers indicates that each project manager has his or her own financial and practical reasons to remain.

The lesser effect was theoretically aligned with the Three-Component Model that was reviewed in Chapter 2. Meyer and Allen (1991, 1997) and Eisenberger et al. (2001) conceptualized Continuance Commitment based on perceptions of costs of leaving as accumulated investments, lack of alternative jobs, or disruption of transition, as opposed to emotional attachment or perceived sense of being valued. Theoretical prediction of this dimension is that POS is only weakly associated with it and meta-analytic results by Meyer et al. (2002) indicated similar attenuated POS-Continuance associations. Naz et al. (2020) also demonstrated that the retention effect of POS flows in a supportive work environment was primarily achieved via affective attachment but not via cost-based attachment, and Pattnaik et al. (2020) also reported that the contextual variables like the person-organization fit were more important than the support perceptions to the continuance dimension. The current finding proved this trend in the Philippine IT consulting environment.

This discovery for the study was a warning to over-depending on economic lock-in strategies as the major retention lever at 77GSI. Non-compete agreements, tenure-based benefits, and retention bonuses slightly enhanced cost-based attachment, but the more significant impacts on Affective commitment ($R^2 = .424$) and Normative commitment

($R^2 = .399$) suggested that relational investment provided greater and more lasting returns on commitment than cost-based strategies alone.

POS Predicting Normative Commitment

POS significantly predicted Normative Commitment, $F(1, 73) = 48.41, p < .001, R^2 = .399, \text{Adjusted } R^2 = .391$. The unstandardized coefficient ($b = 0.780, SE = 0.112, 95\% \text{ CI } [0.557, 1.004]$) was that with an increase in POS by one unit, the change in Normative Commitment was 0.780-unit increase, the steepest of the 4 models. The null H_{04} - POS does not significantly predict Normative commitment among the project managers at 77GSI, was rejected.

The effect of POS on Normative Commitment was 39.9% variance - a huge impact based on Cohen's (1988) standards. The slope ($b = 0.780$), which was unstandardized, was more than the slope of Affective commitment ($b = 0.634$), implying that a one-unit increase in POS would result in a greater increase in obligation-based commitment compared to emotional attachment. Placed in the descriptive profile, Normative Commitment had the highest mean of the three dimensions ($M = 5.02, \text{Slightly High}$) and the dimensional ranking of obligation dominating over affect was contrary to what Western-based studies on TCM had recorded.

The discovery reflects with the cross-cultural part of Chapter 2 review. Eisenberger et al. (2020) reported stronger POS effects to Normative Commitment in Eastern collectivist societies than Western individualist societies and explained it by the higher salience of relational norms of reciprocity and obligation. Meyer and Allen (1997) and Eisenberger et al. (2001) also found moral obligation, indebtedness and perceived duty to

reciprocate as the processes by which POS may enhance Normative Commitment, particularly in relational and collectivist societies. The cultural effect of *utang na loob* (debt of gratitude) in the Philippine context helped to offer a culturally consistent process through which this amplified effect can be achieved: perceived organizational investment will trigger a sense of moral obligation to reciprocate it through loyalty and continued service (Hofstede, 2001; Jocano, 1997). The high coefficient of b (0.780) in the current research was in line with this culturally strengthened pathway.

In the case of 77GSI, the result was that apparent and sustained organizational investment in the well-being of project managers stimulated a culturally based sense of obligation that served as a retention strategy alongside emotional attachment. Support practices that were authentic and publicly accessible, like personal check-ins in escalations, recognition of family or professional milestones, and active home-firm championing of the interests of the project manager in the client settings, were most prone to trigger *utang na loob* processes and elicit stronger normative and affective commitment in this workforce.

Summary of Regression Results

A comprehensive summary of the regression analyses, with the regression coefficients, standard errors, t-values, p-values and confidence intervals for the model was shown in Table 10.

Hypothesis Testing

Based on the regression analyses, the null hypotheses were evaluated as follows:

H₀1: POS does not significantly predict overall OC among project managers at 77GSI.

Result: The null hypothesis was rejected. POS significantly predicted overall Organizational Commitment, $F(1, 73) = 62.35, p < .001, R^2 = .461$.

H₀2: POS does not significantly predict Affective Commitment among project managers at 77GSI.

Result: The null hypothesis was rejected. POS significantly predicted Affective Commitment, $F(1, 73) = 53.68, p < .001, R^2 = .424$.

H₀3: POS does not significantly predict Continuance Commitment among project managers at 77GSI.

Result: The null hypothesis was rejected. POS significantly predicted Continuance Commitment, $F(1, 73) = 7.18, p = .009, R^2 = .090$.

H₀4: POS does not significantly predict Normative Commitment among project managers at 77GSI.

Result: The null hypothesis was rejected. POS significantly predicted Normative Commitment, $F(1, 73) = 48.41, p < .001, R^2 = .399$.

Summary of Findings

The regression model gave a consistent trend. All the four null hypotheses (H₀1-H₀4) were rejected: Perceived Organizational Support had a significant impact on Overall Organizational Commitment ($R^2 = .461$), Affective commitment ($R^2 = .424$), Normative

commitment ($R^2 = .399$), and Continuance commitment ($R^2 = .090$). The effect sizes in relation to Cohen's (1988) benchmarks were large in case of Overall OC, Affective Commitment, and Normative commitment, and small-to-medium in the case of Continuance Commitment. The steepest regression slope was registered on Normative Commitment ($b = 0.780$) which was higher than the slope of Affective Commitment ($b = 0.634$) - an arrangement that flipped the Affective-dominant trend common to Western TCM studies and suggested the cultural enhancement of obligation-based commitment within the Philippine context. Chapter 5 discusses these findings in relation to theory, literature and practice.

CHAPTER V:

DISCUSSION, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Discussion

This chapter analyzes the results from Chapter 4 in terms of the theoretical frameworks presented in Chapter 1 and reviewed in the empirical literature in Chapter 2. The discussion section of this paper is divided into eight (8) thematic areas, namely: (1) Descriptive Profile of POS and Organizational Commitment; (2) POS as a predictor of Overall Organizational Commitment; (3) Reconciling Strong POS Prediction with Persistent Industry Attrition; (4) Differential prediction of the three dimensions of commitment; (5) Cultural Disalignment with Western-Centric OST Predictions; (6) Addressing the Research Gap; (7) the boundary-spanning context of IT consulting; and (8) cultural contextualization in the Philippine context.

Descriptive Profile of POS and Organizational Commitment

A summary of the descriptive results is a valuable background before discussing the predictive relationships. The reported mean of POS score by 77GSI project managers was 5.26 ($SD = 1.012$) which is considered Slightly High according to the verbal interpretation scale. This implies that the project managers, though structurally stationed at the client sites, perceive a Slightly High level of organizational support from their home firm, falling within the 4.44 – 5.29 band of Table 3, which reflects adequate, though not exceedingly high, organizational support in the context of boundary-spanning deployment.

At the item level, the highest-rated POS item was “*Help is available from the organization when I have a problem*” (Item 7; $M = 5.83$, High), then “*The organization*

really cares about my well-being" (Item 8; $M = 5.56$, High), and finally, "*The organization values my contribution to its well-being*" (Item 1; $M = 5.55$, High). The least rated POS measure was the statement as follows: "*If the organization could find somebody to replace me at a lower salary it would do so*" (Item 2; $M = 4.47$, Slightly High), which had the largest variance ($SD = 1.77$), meaning that there is a significant difference in the way project managers view their replacement in the organization.

Normative Commitment was the highest rated out of the three dimensions of commitment ($M = 5.02$, Slightly High) then Continuance Commitment ($M = 4.85$, Slightly High), Affective Commitment ($M = 4.72$, Slightly High). The overall Organizational Commitment had a mean of 4.87 ($SD = 0.90$, Slightly High). The fact that Normative Commitment is the dimension with the highest rating is consistent with the collectivist cultural values present within the Philippine workplace, where *utang na loob* (debt of gratitude) and *pakikisama* (smooth interpersonal relations) contribute to the development of a strong sense of obligation to the organization (Hofstede, 2001; Jocano, 1997). These descriptive results will give background information on the following regression results.

These descriptive patterns have practical implications to 77GSI leadership and organization development practitioners. The mean of slightly high POS ($M = 5.26$) confirms that the support mechanisms that are in place are functional, yet the item level spread (between the highest $M = 5.83$ on problem-availability (Item 7) to the lowest $M = 4.47$ on replaceability concerns (Item 2)) indicates the areas of risk that are concentrated where the perceived support is most flexible and unpredictable. Likewise, the commitment profile (obligation) in which Normative commitment ($M = 5.02$) surpasses over Affective commitment ($M = 4.72$) that present practices have elicited this sense of obligation more

easily than the emotional belonging. This difference should guide the effort to design the support interventions: the development of affective attachment between the project managers as boundary-spanners needs to be informed by intentional, interpersonal, and evident displays of care, rather than by mere adherence to the support procedures.

POS as a Predictor of Organizational Commitment

Results of the simple linear regression indicated that POS significantly predicted Overall Organizational Commitment ($F(1, 73) = 62.35, p < .001, R^2 = .461$), accounting for 46.1% of the variance in OC — a large effect exceeding Cohen's (1988) benchmark of $R^2 = .26$. The unstandardized regression coefficient ($b = 0.598$) confirmed that for each one-unit increase in POS, Overall OC increased by 0.598 units. Both POS ($M = 5.26$, Slightly High) and Overall OC ($M = 4.87$, Slightly High) fell within the same verbal interpretation band (4.44 – 5.29; Table 3), reflecting a coherent profile of organizational orientation among the respondent project managers.

This lends significant support for the core notion of Organizational Support Theory (OST): when employees feel that their organization values their contributions to the organization and is concerned about their well-being, in return they react by developing greater psychological attachment to the firm (Eisenberger et al., 1986; Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002).

The magnitude of this predictive relationship is of particular interest in the context of the work context of project managers, which is boundary spanning and client embedded. As stated by Boundary Spanning Theory (Aldrich & Herker, 1977; Marchington et al., 2005), the people who are deployed across organizational boundaries are exposed

to structural and psychological distance from their home employer, thus potentially reducing home-organization attachment. Yet we can see that POS does indeed account for almost half of the variance in OC, underlining the perception of being valued and supported by 77GSI remains a dominant psychological force even when day-to-day work is being carried out at client sites.

These results are in line with meta-analytic results from Rhoades and Eisenberger in 2002 and Kurtessis et al. in 2017 that revealed strong POS-OC relationships in a variety of organizational contexts. They are also in line with Andrin and Dumale (2023) who found significant POS-OC correlations among local government employees in the Philippines, and Suárez-Albanchez et al. (2022) who showed that organizational support is a key protective factor for turnover intentions in the Spanish IT consultancy industry. From a Social Exchange Theory perspective (Blau, 1964; Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005), the results support the idea that 77GSI project managers engage in reciprocal exchange: that is, when organizational care goes beyond contractual obligations and they reciprocate by giving added commitment to the firm.

Cultural Disalignment with Western-Centric OST Predictions

One should note that the trend recorded in this study was quite a significant deviation of theoretical expectation of Organizational Support Theory, and of the general results found in Western organizational behavior studies. The results of the meta-analyses of Rhoades and Eisenberger (2002) and Kurtessis et al. (2017) indicated that OST, as originally theorized by Eisenberger et al. (1986) and verified in these meta-analyses, suggested that POS would most strongly correlate with affective commitment, since the perception of organizational care directly satisfied the socioemotional Affective

commitment has been found in most studies carried out in North American and European environments to be the most strongly predicted dimension of commitment by POS.

Nevertheless, Normative Commitment had the highest rating ($M = 5.02$) in the current study as well as the most sharply predicted by POS ($b = 0.780$), which is greater than the Affective Commitment coefficient ($b = 0.634$). The Filipino cultural value of *utang na loob* can account to such cultural disalignment, a sense of debt or obligation that is so ingrained and deep within the individual, which occurs when he or she feels that another party has given him or her actual, voluntary care or support (Jocano, 1997; Enriquez, 1992). In contrast to transactional reciprocity, *utang na loob* is a sustained moral relationship: as 77GSI project managers felt that their organization sincerely cared about their welfare and appreciated their efforts, this belief triggered a culturally charged sense of moral responsibility to stay and work, which became evident in the form of high normative commitment.

This was in line with Eisenberger et al. (2020) who discovered that the effects of POS on obligation-based commitment were more pronounced in Eastern collectivist societies where relational reciprocity and group harmony took precedence. This dynamic was further supported by the cultural value of *pakikisama*, the Filipino focus on ensuring that there is smooth interpersonal interaction and group cohesiveness (Hofstede, 2001) which made it socially expensive to abandon an organization that was deemed to be conducive. The normative commitment pathway could have been activated in this cultural background as the main process by which POS was converted into organization attachment, not incompatible with the main logic of OST but possibly in a culturally different path that the Western-based models had not foreseen fully.

This cultural finding directly applies to the workplace practice in the area of how 77GSI designs facilitate messaging and recognition frameworks. Relational (as opposed to transactional) support practices will be more likely to elicit the *utang na loob* mechanism and transform perceived support into normative commitment. In particular, managers supervising deployed project managers are to convey how the organization recognizes their personal and professional sacrifice involved in boundary-spanning jobs: once employees feel that organizational support is not only contractual, but is also voluntary, the sense of moral obligation embedded in the cultures becomes more pronounced. The practical mediums through which such a culturally calibrated support pathway is best triggered are recognition programs, presence of career advocates in times of client escalation and personalized leadership outreach in the event of long deployment.

Reconciling Strong POS Prediction with Persistent Industry Attrition

A significant interpretive factor that emerged based on these findings was that there appeared to be a conflict between the high predictability of POS on OC ($R^2 = .461$) and the significantly high rate of attrition (22.6%) in the Philippine consulting industry (Aon, 2025). When POS explained close to half of the variability in organizational commitment, the question raised was why was there still high attrition in the industry?

This paradox may be solved by acknowledging that organizational commitment and actual turnover are different constructs that are related to each other. Commitment is a psychological relationship -- an attitude of attachment, duty, or perceived expense whereas turnover is a behavioral consequence and is affected by other factors other than the psychology of the individual (Meyer and Allen, 1991; Griffeth et al., 2000). There were

a number of external pull factors that were independent of POS and commitment in determining the actual attrition performance in the Philippine IT consulting industry.

First, the world demand of IT project managers led to a very competitive external labor market where professionals would get unsolicited offers by multinational companies and offshore delivery centers without considering their level of commitment to their present employer (Aon, 2025). Second, the presence of compensation differentials was an effective external incentive: even in the case of being supported and committed, much higher salary proposals of rival companies could override the psychological adhesion especially when the financial needs (housing, education, family support) were acute (Hom et al., 2017). Third, career mobility goals, such as the need to climb the hierarchy, exposure to new technologies, or a change in product-based firms, were pull factors that could not be resolved only through organizational support (Presbitero et al., 2016).

The 53.9% of the variance in OC not accounted by POS was probably due to these external market forces, individual career stage factors and structural influences like competitiveness of compensation, benefits parity and career development opportunities. This observation highlighted the practical implication that even though POS was a requisite, and a potent internal retention mechanism, it alone could not totally mitigate the external forces compelling attrition in the Philippine consulting industry. An effective retention plan would thus require an integrated approach to support practices based on POS with competitive pay plans, career development initiatives, and active management of talent risk.

Differential Prediction Across Commitment Dimensions

A major contribution of this study is that it examined the differential prediction of the three components of OC by POS. POS had the strongest statistical predictive validity for Affective Commitment ($R^2 = .424$) and Normative Commitment ($R^2 = .399$) followed by a considerably weaker, but statistically significant and psychometrically sound prediction of Continuance Commitment ($R^2 = .090$). More importantly, the substantive differences in R^2 across the three subscales -- large effects for Affective and Normative Commitment versus a small effect for Continuance Commitment -- are consistent with the theoretical expectations of the Three-Component Model and Organizational Support Theory, indicating that these are real differences in predictive strength rather than measurement artifacts.

Affective Commitment

The prediction of Affective Commitment by way of POS ($R^2 = .424$, $b = 0.634$, $p < .001$) confirms the theoretically expected primary linkage in the OST. Rhoades and Eisenberger (2002) and Kurtessis et al. (2017) consistently find affective commitment to be the dimension most strongly related to POS arguing that perceived organizational care meets socioemotional needs for approval, affiliation, and self-esteem and hence fosters emotional attachment. For boundary-spanning project managers at 77GSI, emotional bond to the parent organization is the main anchor of home-firm identification and POS seems to powerfully maintain such an anchor in conditions of client-site deployment. This finding is similar with those from Indonesian and Philippine studies (Astuty & Udin, 2020; Nurfayani & Wibawa, 2022; Andrin & Dumale, 2023) and also similar with those from Silva

et al. (2022) which demonstrated the direct effects of POS on affective commitment in several professional settings.

Practically, this observation suggests that the support systems used by 77GSI, especially those that communicate sincerity and appreciation of efforts as opposed to merely financial rewards, are most effective in motivating home-firm emotional attachment of the project in the case of boundary-spanning project managers. The substantial effect size ($R^2 = .424$) indicates that even small increases in perceived organizational care, including recognition at the right time in project milestones or during client escalations by the leadership, can be significant contributors to affective commitment amongst the deployed workforces.

Normative Commitment

The large prediction of Normative Commitment by POS ($R^2 = .399$, $b = 0.780$, $p < .001$) has strong theoretical and cultural underpinnings. Meyer and Allen (1997) and Eisenberger et al. (2001) proposed that POS increase or amplifies normative commitment by a sense of moral obligation and indebtedness, psychological mechanisms that are particularly salient in collectivist cultures. In the Philippine context, the cultural concept of *utang na loob* -- debt of gratitude -- offers a very powerful amplifier for this dynamic: when the project managers perceive that 77GSI is truly investing in their well-being and recognizing their contributions, they feel a strong moral obligation to reciprocate by staying and contributing (Hofstede, 2001; Jocano, 1997). The higher regression coefficient for Normative Commitment ($b = 0.780$) compared to Affective Commitment ($b = 0.634$) shows that for each unit increase in POS, the obligatory dimension of commitment increased

more sharply than the emotional dimension of commitment in the present sample. This is in line with Eisenberger et al. (2020) who found stronger POS effects in Eastern collectivist cultures and generalizes to the Filipino IT consulting professionals.

This trend can be empirically supported by Artatanaya et al. (2023) who showed that even simple forms of organizational appreciation were significant predictors of organizational commitment in the small-to-medium enterprise context and with Sadaf et al. (2022) who also contributed that perceived organizational support and organizational value systems were important predictors of organizational commitment. Suárez-Albanchez et al. (2022) in the IT consultancy industry discovered that the stronger the organizational support perceived by the consultants the higher the affective and normative commitment, which results in a drastic reduction of turnover intentions - the same steep normative prediction as observed in the current study ($b = 0.780$).

The salience of Normative Commitment in the current results is also in line with the give-and-take mechanism central to Social Exchange Theory (Blau, 1964; Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005). When employees experience a sense of more organizational support than they need by a contract — and this impression is reflected in the higher evaluated SPOS items with regard to something people really care about and that are available to help — employees experience a sense of indebtedness that inspires them to make good on their indebtedness by obligatory staying behaviors. In collectivist cultural situations like the Philippines, such a norm of reciprocity is fostered socially such that organizational investment perceivably generate not only emotional desire to stay, but a moral imperative to do so (Eisenberger et al., 2001; Hofstede, 2001). The higher regression indicated for Normative Commitment ($b = 0.780$) compared to Affective

Commitment ($b = 0.634$) is hence interpretable in terms of both OST and SET at the same time: POS meets socioemotional needs which create emotional attachment by together triggering obligations of reciprocity which create a sense of duty.

This finding has direct implications to the retention strategy of 77GSI in the workplace practice. Since perceived moral obligation triggers normative commitment, visible and personalized, long-lasting organizational investment, like sponsoring professional growth, promoting project managers through client conflicts, and constant well-being outreach during long deployments, is likely to result in culturally reinforced loyalty that is not just a product of emotional attachment.

Continuance Commitment

The prediction of Continuance Commitment by POS ($R^2 = .090$, $b = 0.380$, $p = .009$) needs a cautious interpretation but is definitely confident. The effect is small — POS only explains less than 10% of variance in this dimension — and, theoretically, this is to be expected. OST and the Three-Component Model tend to predict a weaker relationship between POS and continuance commitment because the latter is based on perceptions of costs of leaving (loss of benefits, disruption of life, limited job alternatives) rather than feelings of emotional bonds or felt obligation (Meyer & Allen, 1991; Eisenberger et al., 2001). There is this seemingly small but significant finding that is directionally consistent with theory: perceived organizational support has some modest capacity to shape cost-based retention cognitions, perhaps by increasing the perceived value of accumulated organizational investments (e.g., tenure-linked benefits, project knowledge, professional relationships built through the firm). The statistical significance of this prediction ($p = .009$)

and the narrow confidence interval for the regression coefficient (95% CI [0.097, 0.662]) lend credibility to this small but real effect.

This is a trend that is in line with general empirical literature. In their meta-analysis of antecedents of commitment, Meyer et al. (2002) discovered that continuance commitment is always weakly correlated with support-related antecedents than affective or normative commitment, which is also observed in different samples. Similar results were obtained by Naz et al. (2020), who showed that although a supportive working environment positively affects retention, the mechanism is mediated by affective commitment and secondary by cost-based attachment. Pattnaik et al. (2020) have determined that person-organization fit can considerably enhance the positive relationship between POS and organizational commitment, which points to the fact that contextual alignment may be more important than support perceptions in the context of the continuance dimension.

Practically, this finding acts as a warning to 77GSI leadership to not place too much reliance on economic lock-in strategies like retention bonuses, non-compete agreements, or tenure-based benefits as the main retention manager tool. Although these strategies have a relatively small impact on the cost-based retention, the significantly higher impacts on the affective commitment ($R^2 = .424$) and normative commitment ($R^2 = .399$) indicate that the relational investment produces higher and more sustainable returns on commitment than mere financial compensation does.

Addressing the Research Gap

The research focused on specifically defined population and knowledge gaps in the POS-OC literature (Miles, 2017). Although POS and organizational commitment are more established constructs that have been widely researched in the traditional employment context, there was very little empirical data on project managers in the context of project-based IT consulting in the Philippines, especially in terms of project-based, boundary-spanning, client-based arrangements. Rhoades and Eisenberger (2002) and Kurtessis et al. (2017) recommended the extension of research on POS to less-explored jobs and groups. Specifically, Suárez-Albanchez et al. (2022) have identified a lack of studies investigating organizational commitment within the IT consultancy industry despite the high turnover rates in the industry. Turner and Muller (2003) also revealed that minimal studies had been done to explore the contribution of organizational-level variables like POS in developing the commitment of project managers in particular.

This study contributes to the gaps by offering context-specific empirical evidence by conducting research on the POS-OC predictive relationship in a sample of 75 project managers in 77GSI, an IT consulting firm in the Philippines, where project managers are boundary spanners who are deployed to work in the client organizations. The results indicate that POS is a major predictor of the three dimensions of commitment in this previously unstudied group and the pattern of differentiation (strongest affective and normative commitment, weakest continuance commitment) in dimension-level prediction that previous studies that treated OC as a global construct had failed to provide (Mowday et al., 1982; Mathieu and Zajac, 1990). The cross-cultural extension of the Organizational

Support Theory specifically to the Philippine IT consulting sector is furthered by the cultural finding on the steep normative commitment prediction (Eisenberger et al., 2020).

The cross-contextual gap result has an underlying strategic caution to practitioners: even retention frameworks with extensive meta-analytical evidence from the Western studies might not directly apply to the Philippine IT consulting context. This pattern of differential prediction report, especially the steep normative commitment trajectory enhanced by *utang na loob*, implies that HR and OD practitioners in 77GSI must not go on blindly following generic global POS frameworks. Rather, the support interventions should be culturally tuned: the relational investment that is observed by deployed project managers and is expressed using a messaging tone that considers individual sacrifices and organizational reciprocity is the evidence-based method that the current study has validated as the most effective in relation to this workforce.

Implications for Boundary Spanners in IT Consulting

The results have a special theoretical significance if we understand them in relation to Boundary Spanning Theory (Aldrich & Herker, 1977; Marchington et al., 2005). Project Manager(s) at 77GSI are assigned at the client site, work within the client organizational cultures and juggle competing expectations of their home firm and the client organization. As Vora and Kostova (2007) and Webber (2011) presents such dynamics of dual identification might complicate commitment to the home firm and lead to psychological drift risks towards the client organization.

However, in this regard, what is striking is the finding that POS explains 46.1% of Overall OC variance: The structural obstacles of working across boundaries

notwithstanding, the degree to which project managers feel valued and supported by 77GSI is the dominant predictor of their commitment to the firm. This is consistent with the Job Demands-Resources Model (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007) in which POS can act as a higher-order organizational resource buffering the demands and strains of working with intensive client-facing roles - tight deadlines, ambiguous authority, complex stakeholder ecosystems - and maintaining engagement and loyalty to the parent organization.

At the item level, the SPOS item with the highest rating, which is the “Help is available from the organization when I have a problem” (Item 7; $M = 5.83$), deserves a particular consideration of the JD-R approach. POS is an elevated tier organizational resource in the sphere of the JD-R framework, as such, it is an indication of resource availability in situations of demand (Bakker and Demerouti, 2007; Kurtessis et al, 2017). The information that the home organization will provide a helping hand when it is required, though, is the motivational resource that ought to offer the project manager struggling with client escalation and unclear authority and complex stakeholder ecosystems the most likely to maintain engagement and provide a buffer to the strain, as is most likely true of the positive predictive effects of Affective and Normative Commitment in this study.

The findings may also be accounted for in the terms of Social Identity Theory (Tajfel & Turner, 1979; Ashforth & Mael, 1989). Project managers deployed in client-embedded arrangements are at structural risk to develop the dual organizational identifications -- simultaneous psychological attachment to both the home consulting firm and the client organization (Vora & Kostova, 2007; Webber, 2011). Social Identity Theory would lead to expectation that in the course of prolonged client-site engagements the salience of home-firm identity will be due to integration decrease, thus providing the

environment for psychological drift. The strong predictive power of POS over Affective Commitment ($R^2 = .424$) in the present study suggests, however, that active organizational support from 77GSI serves as a psychological tether that maintains home-firm identification, despite the conditions of lengthened deployment at client sites. This seems consistent with Webber's (2011) finding that project managers who maintain simultaneous identification report higher personal attachment to the parent firm, and this actually suggests that support practices which serve to consistently signal home-firm membership - recognition, visibility, career advocacy - may work to actively counter the effects of identity drift in boundary spanning roles.

The great predictive power of Affective Commitment suggests that it is the emotional bond, and not economic calculus, that best nurtures in boundary-spanning workers. For organizational practice, this means that support mechanisms that cause project managers to feel that they are truly valued and cared for — as opposed to just retained by financial incentives — are the most consequential investments in home-firm commitment. This finding is an extension of the work of Li et al., (2022) who argued the need to further explore the dynamics of POS-commitment in specific boundary spanner professional contexts and of Verweij et al. (2023) who identified top management support as an important driver of boundary spanner functioning and commitment.

In the workplace context, the implication of these results is that 77GSI ought to make proactive support touchpoints to project managers in cases of long-lasting client-site deployments, including periodic non-project check-ins with the leadership of the home-firm, participation in internal community activities, and observable career advocacy indicating ongoing membership in the home-firm. Gantman and Fedorowicz (2011)

reasoned, that the intensive communication demands of project managers deployed require mature practices of boundary-spanning within organizations, which support the current results that empirically prove these practices are not only effective in operational coordination but also psychological attachment to the parent firm.

Contextualizing Findings in the Philippine Setting

The results are in contextual situation in the deepest sense relating to the culture. The Philippine workplace is characterized by collectivist values, obligation to relationships (*pakikisama*), and expectations within the organization as a paternalistic need that an organization will care for their employees in a familial way (Church, 1986; Alampay, 2014). These cultural dynamics make POS-OC relationship stronger, particularly on the normative dimension. The finding that Normative Commitment is both the commitment dimension that is the most highly rated ($M = 5.02$) as well as the most steeply predicted by POS ($b = 0.780$) is consistent with the moral-related power of *utang na loob* in this context: When the organization is felt to be genuinely supportive, the Filipino employees are deeply obliged to reciprocate with loyalty and continued service.

The item level finding "Help is available from the organization when I have a problem" (Item 7; $M = 5.83$) is the highest rated POS item that reflects the attitude Filipino employees place on organizational responsiveness in times of individual and professional need that is consistent with paternalistic relationship expectations documented in the literature (Church, 1986; Alampay, 2014). Eisenberger et al. (2020) found that the effects of POS tend to be more prominent in Eastern collectivist cultures than in Western individualist cultures and they attributed it to the higher salience of the socioemotional motivations of belonging, esteem and reciprocity of obligation. The current findings provide

support to this cross-cultural finding among the Philippine IT consulting industry in particular.

This cultural dynamic recorded in this study is also supported by Philippine specific empirical evidence. In their study, Andrin and Dumale (2023) discovered that there were strong positive relationships between organizational support, and employee commitment among local government employees in Surigao City, which shows that the POS–commitment relationship is universal within Philippine organizational settings. Artatanaya et al. (2023) demonstrated that organizational appreciation is a predictor of commitment even in resource-constrained environments, which supports the idea that the importance of support perceptions is especially high in the cultures where the idea of relational reciprocity is one of the core values.

Practically, the findings of these cultures imply that intervention support at 77GSI must be modeled in a sensitive way to Filipino relational expectations. Informal, personalized displays of care should be added to formal recognition programs - in line with the paternalistic style of leadership that Filipino employees react positively to (Church, 1986; Alampay, 2014). To the boundary-spanning project managers, it implies that home-firm leaders personally making contact at challenging stages in the project, recognizing family or personal achievements, and becoming a visible champion of the interests of their project managers are likely engaging the culturally specific processes of *utang na loob* that lead to enduring normative and affective commitment.

Limitations of the Study

It is also necessary to acknowledge that several limitations deserve mention. First, the cross-sectional design makes it impossible to perform strict experimental causal inference; though POS is modeled as a causal antecedent of OC consistent with ex post facto causal research design (Cohen et al., 2018), longitudinal or experimental designs would yield better causal warrant.

Second, the study is limited to 77GSI's Philippine IT consulting operations and replication to other firms, industries, or national contexts is needed before broader conclusions can be drawn.

Third, common method bias is an issue inherent in single source self-report surveys (Podsakoff et al., 2003); psychological separators were used between the POS and OC survey sections to reduce the potential for this source of variance.

Fourth, the final sample of $N = 75$, while maintaining minimum requirements (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970; Green, 1991), is relatively small.

Fifth, POS was conceptualized as a unidimensional construct based on the 8-item SPOS (Eisenberger et al., 1986), which fails to differentiate between particular kinds of organizational support, e.g., socioemotional and instrumental support. As a result, this research is unable to define the specific dimensions of POS that are most likely to influence commitment. Future studies ought to design or borrow multidimensional POS measures to find out whether socioemotional (e.g., care, recognition, respect) and instrumental (e.g., tangible resources, conflict support, decision latitude) support can differentially predict affective, continuance and normative commitment levels among

boundary-spanning project managers. This refining would allow more narrowly focused support interventions.

Sixth, the researcher announced that a token of appreciation will be presented to the PMO Manager and Client Delivery manager, being the decision makers, as shown in Appendix H, which may have an effect to this behavioral study.

Conclusions

This study investigated the ability of POS to significantly predict OC of Project Managers at 77GSI. Based on data received from 75 project managers using simple linear regression, the following conclusion can be drawn.

First, POS is an important and significant predictor of Overall Organizational Commitment, and its variance explains 46.1%. This validates the central proposition of OST in the context of boundary-spanning project managers in the Philippine IT consulting sector: that globally, the perceived values of the organization that one contributes to and the concern that one's well-being is taken care of is a strong determinant for psychological attachment in the organization.

Second, POS is shown to have a selective predictive capacity, across dimensions of OC. It is associated with the strongest and the most predictable relationship with Affective Commitment ($R^2 = .424$) and Normative Commitment ($R^2 = .399$), which is weaker but statistically significant for Continuance Commitment ($R^2 = .090$). All the four null hypotheses were rejected. Emotional attachment, sense of obligation are the main

mediums in which POS works where the retention cognitions based on cost are affected by POS to a lesser extent.

Third, the significant regression coefficient of Normative Commitment ($b = 0.780$) is higher than Affective Commitment ($b = 0.634$), which shows the moral-relational power of *utang na loob* in the Philippine cultural context, in which perceived organizational investment produces strong felt obligation. This finding extends the cross-cultural application of Eisenberger et al. (2020) specifically to the Philippine IT consulting industry.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are addressed to key stakeholders.

Proposed Management Development Program (MDP)

Based on the empirical findings of this study, a proposed Management Development Program (MDP) is presented in Table 11 below. The program is structured around the item-level POS results, leveraging the three highest-rated support areas as points of strength to be sustained and institutionalized, and targeting the three lowest-rated areas as points for improvement requiring focused intervention. The three highest-rated POS items were: "Help is available from the organization when I have a problem." (Item 7; $M = 5.83$), "The organization really cares about my well-being (Item 8; $M = 5.56$), and "The organization values my contribution to its well-being (Item 1; $M = 5.55$). The three lowest-rated POS items were: "If the organization could hire someone to replace me at a lower salary, it would do so." (Item 2; $M = 4.47$), "The organization disregards my best interests when it makes decisions that affect me (Item 6; $M = 5.08$), and "The organization

fails to appreciate any extra effort from me (Item 3; $M = 5.11$). The program design links each POS area to the specific commitment dimensions most strongly predicted by POS – affective commitment ($R^2 = .424$) and normative commitment ($R^2 = .399$) – to ensure that interventions are empirically grounded and strategically targeted.

Table 11

Proposed Management Development Program (MDP) for Project Managers at 77GSI

POS Area	Diagnostic Finding	Target OC Dimension	Recommended Interventions	Primary Owner
POINTS OF STRENGTH (Sustain & Institutionalize)				
Help Availability (Item 7; <i>M</i> = 5.83, High)	Project managers perceive strong organizational responsiveness when problems arise	Affective Commitment (<i>R</i> ² = .424)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Institutionalize escalation-response SLAs for deployed PMs Maintain accessible coaching and peer-consultation channels Conduct quarterly “support responsiveness” pulse checks Sustain non-project check-ins for client-deployed PMs 	PMO Leads, Delivery Leaders
Genuine Care for Well-Being (Item 8; <i>M</i> = 5.56, High)	Project managers feel the organization authentically cares about their welfare	Normative Commitment (<i>R</i> ² = .399)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implement well-being touchpoints (workload reviews, mental health resources) Leadership visibility through personalized outreach Formalize recognition programs (delivery milestones, extra-role contributions) 	HR/OD, Senior Leaders
Valuing Contributions (Item 1; <i>M</i> = 5.55, High)	Project managers feel their contributions are recognized by the organization	Affective + Normative Commitment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Create visibility channels for PM achievements (internal newsletters, town halls) Tie recognition to career progression criteria 	Senior Leaders, HR/OD
POINTS FOR IMPROVEMENT (Focused Intervention)				
Replaceability Concerns (Item 2; <i>M</i> = 4.47, Slightly High)	Mixed perceptions about whether the organization would replace PMs for cost savings; highest variance (<i>SD</i> = 1.77)	Affective Commitment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communicate the strategic and unique value of PM roles explicitly Invest in PM-specific upskilling and certification sponsorship Establish career pathing that signals long-term investment in PMs 	Senior Leaders, HR/OD
Decision-Making Considerations (Item 6; <i>M</i> = 5.08, Slightly High)	Room for improvement in considering PM interests in organizational decisions	Normative Commitment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Include PM representatives in governance and policy discussions Establish feedback loops before decisions affecting deployed staff Transparent communication on rationale for organizational decisions Implement peer-nominated and manager-nominated recognition for discretionary effort 	Senior Leaders, PMO Leads
Appreciation of Extra Effort (Item 3; <i>M</i> = 5.11, Slightly High)	Moderate perception that extra effort goes unrecognized	Affective + Normative Commitment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Acknowledge stretch performance during project closures and reviews Link extra-role contributions to performance evaluations and incentives 	Delivery Leaders, HR/OD

Note. POS item means and commitment *R*² values from the study findings (*N* = 75). Verbal interpretations based on the equal-interval scale (Table 3). Program structure addresses

points of strength (sustain) and points for improvement (intervene) as recommended by the oral defense panel.

It should be mentioned that in this study, POS was determined as a unidimensional measure; the SPOS does not provide individual subscales of different forms of support. The item-level analysis that should be employed to organize the proposed program is thus an operational approximation as opposed to a dimensional decomposition. Future studies using multidimensional POS measures would further perfect the support interventions targeting (see Limitations and Future Research Directions).

For Senior Leaders and Organizational Executives

As organizational commitment based on POS (46.1% of the overall variance) is a strategic organizational retention investment, the senior leadership of 77GSI needs to view organizational support as a strategic organizational retention investment. The findings of the study are operationalized into a structured framework in the proposed Management Development Program (MDP) shown in Table 11. Specifically, by discussing the low replaceability perception (Item 2; $M = 4.47$) as the lowest rated POS item with the highest response variance, explicit communication of the distinct value of project managers skills and institutional knowledge would be endorsing the area that has the most uncertain and probably the most amenable perceptions.

For Human Resources and Organizational Development Practitioners

The support-based programs that the HR and OD professionals should develop need to address the POS aspects that have the highest means: practical help availability (Item 7; $M = 5.83$) and genuine care about well-being (Item 8; $M = 5.56$). Making

responsive assistance in case of project escalation institutional, ensuring access to internal coaching and peer consultation and structured channels for feedback between the deployed project managers and their functional leaders will make POS strong in its most effective points. This fact that continuance commitment cost-based retention is predicted by POS at only a weak effect ($R^2 = .090$) is a warning against over-reliance upon economic lock-in strategies as a retention strategy; relational investment generates greater and longer-lasting commitment. It is also suggested to develop POS-oriented capability development in direct supervisors since they have already been identified as channels of organizational support perceptions (Eisenberger et al., 2002).

For People Managers, Delivery Leaders, and PMO or Practice Leads

The POS-Affective and POS-Normative Findings can be directly applied in day-to-day management. Support behaviors, such as timely and material feedback, advocacy of workload, and acknowledgment of extra-role performance as well as ongoing presence during client escalations need to be integrated into governance routines and not necessarily only taken up during formal performance cycles. The behaviors are indicators of organizational care and valuation which are the proximal antecedents of POS. Managers who have project managers dealing with long-term client engagement are to plan frequent non-project check-ins that remind the project manager that s/he is a member and part of the 77GSI community and eliminate the risk of gradual identity decay towards the client organization.

For Project Managers

The findings confirm that the assistance that the support project managers get through 77GSI is significantly linked with the sense of belonging and loyalty, in addition to

perceived obligation to the firm. Project managers are also urged to express their support requires with vigor as the results show that perceived organizational support when experienced is a strong force of commitment. Knowledge of this relationship could enable project managers to make discussions of recognition, workload, and career development as valid investments in organizations but not requests.

For Future Researchers

Several directions for future research are recommended. In terms of research methods, a longitudinal study is recommended to track POS-OC dynamics over the lifecycle of client engagements in order to check if perceived support attenuates over the lifetime of long deployments, and if targeted interventions can keep it alive. Research that includes mediating variables -- job satisfaction, psychological empowerment, leader-member exchange and dual organizational identification -- would shed light the mechanisms by which POS affects OC in this context (Maan et al., 2020; Silva et al., 2022; Vora & Kostova, 2007). Comparative multi-firm research studies within the Philippine IT consulting industry would improve the external validity and enhance the generalizability of these findings. Qualitative research concerning the subjective experience of home organization support by project managers working in client embedded arrangements would complement the quantitative findings reported here.

In summary, this study presents empirical evidence that POS is a significant predictor for OC -- most powerfully for Affective and Normative Commitment -- amongst Project Managers at 77GSI. As attrition pressures in the Philippine consulting sector remain elevated (Aon, 2025), the use of organizational support practices that convey to

project managers that they are genuinely valued, felt helped and cared for by their home organization is both empirically based and also a good business strategy.

CHAPTER VI:

BENEDICTINE LEARNINGS

This chapter provides a shift from the empirical findings and theoretical interpretations presented in the preceding chapters to a reflection of the goodness of fit of the predictive relationship between Perceived Organizational Support (POS) and Organizational Commitment (OC) to the Benedictine hallmarks. As a student in the MBA program at San Beda College Alabang, the researcher posits that integrating such statistical data with the teaching of St. Benedict's vision provides a broader framework for understanding human behavior and management practices within the workplace.

The basic aim of this research was to examine the cause antecedent of POS on the result variable of OC. While the findings support modern organizational theories, they also empirically support centuries-old Benedictine wisdom about the ways communities are built, sustained and nurtured.

The cornerstone of Benedictine spirituality is "Ora et Labora"—the vital balance between prayer (contemplation and reflection) and work (action and execution). The Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model utilized in this study provides a theoretical framework for interpreting these findings. For project managers at 77GSI, *Labora* is clearly manifested in the boundary-spanning demands of their roles: delivering complex IT projects, meeting stringent client deadlines, and navigating intricate stakeholder ecosystems.

However, *Labora* never stopped acting to a counteracting force, for burnout and attrition. In this case, Perceived Organizational Support is to an organization as *Ora* is to

That in all things, God may be glorified

an individual. It is the intentional care and reflective support of socioemotional care provided by the home firm. The data revealed that the POS is accounting for 46.1% variances of Overall Organizational Commitment. This strong predictive power over organizational commitment is the validation of the idea of *Ora et Labora*: when an organization is able to actively balance the high demands from the projects that are being delivered and a genuine and structured organizational support, the firm will build a very committed and resistant workforce.

The Rule of St. Benedict holds the Abbot responsible for the care of the physical and spiritual well-being of the community in a big way. Seeing through the lens of Organizational Support Theory (OST), this is a stewardship that is operationalized as POS. The empirical evidence shows that project managers are not just resources to be utilized for the benefit of the client to be billed, but individuals who require holistic care.

At the level of individual indicators, the best-performing SPOS indicator was "*Help is available from the organization when I have a problem*" ($M = 5.83$). When leaders are true stewards — when they make sure that practical assistance and genuine concern is readily available — they are living up to this Benedictine mandate. The commitment received from employees is a natural reciprocation of that stewardship.

The concept of *Stabilitas*, or the vow of stability, represents a commitment to remain in a specific community throughout one's life, through both trials and triumphs. Within the framework of operations, this stability was measured in terms of Organizational Commitment. The regression models in Chapter 4 demonstrated POS are more highly related to Affective Commitment ($R^2 = .424$) and Normative Commitment ($R^2 = .399$), but

a much weaker relationship exists between POS and Continuance Commitment ($R^2 = .090$).

This differential prediction is deeply in line with Benedictine thought. It implies that the authentic stability in an IT consulting firm cannot be designed by economic need and financial lock-ins only (Continuance Commitment). Instead, it is stability that is the emotional and moral response to feeling valued. In the Philippine setting, this is strengthened by the cultural concept of *utang na loob*; when the organization invests heavily in the well-being of its boundary spanners; this generates a natural moral obligation (i.e. Normative Commitment) to stay and contribute and a genuine desire (i.e. Affective Commitment) to stay and contribute.

The Benedictine value of respect for people requires the leader to consider the unique dignity and special problems of each person. Boundary Spanning Theory is all about the type of structural and psychological isolation that the project managers are likely to experience if they are completely subsumed in client environments.

Applying "respect for people" means that 77GSI leadership must be actively listening and affording these unique stressors. By institutionalizing ways of proactively supporting them, while keeping the lines of communication strong, and ensuring that project managers do not succumb to an identity decay towards the client organization, the firm regards the dignity of the firm's boundary spanners. It makes sure that they are bound to their home organization even when physically they are away from the organization.

Ultimately, the causal relationship of the POS to the OC ($X \rightarrow O$), is not just a statistical phenomenon, but rather it is a reflection of human nature. In order to preserve

the talent pool for its organization against the high rates of attrition in the Philippine consulting industry, organizations have to look beyond strictly transactional management. In this chapter, in taking on Benedictine Learnings and Wisdom of Ora et Labora, Stewardship and Respect for Persons, leadership can create an environment where highly skilled professionals remain not because they have to, but because they feel supported, valued and really part of the community.

On a personal note, this research journey has demonstrated that leadership begins with a sincere regard for the people being led—a lesson that aligns with the Benedictine principle of Stewardship. Furthermore, effective leadership of others requires the ability to lead oneself, which introduces the next guiding principle.

From the early stages of the MBA program, the Benedictine principle of Moderation served as a cornerstone of this journey. This principle enabled a vital balance between professional duties as a Project Manager and the commitment to completing MBA studies, necessitating the sacrifice of social activities and leisure. Moreover, moderation proved essential in managing parental responsibilities for a newborn, Magnus Aurelius. This disciplined approach prevented burnout and exhaustion, particularly during December 2025, when five subjects were taken simultaneously for the Written Comprehensive Exam alongside preparations for the Thesis 1 Defense.

Perhaps the most significant Benedictine principle regarding this thesis is Obedience. Without the application of this principle, the manuscript may not have gained necessary traction. By remaining open and obedient to the recommendations of the thesis

adviser and panelists, the researcher was able to craft a manuscript that reflects rigorous guidance and professional pride.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A Informed Consent Form

San Beda College Alabang
8 Don Manolo Blvd., Alabang Hills Village,
Muntinlupa City, 1770

Research Ethics Committee Informed Consent Form

Research Title: Perceived Organizational Support and Organizational Commitment: A Predictive Study among Project Managers at 77GSI

Principal Researcher: Savipra Alexandrio D. Gorospe

Introduction

We are MBA students from San Beda College Alabang, and we would like to invite you to participate in our research about Perceived Organizational Support and Organizational Commitment among Project Managers at 77GSI. The purpose of this research is to determine whether Perceived Organizational Support (POS) predicts Organizational Commitment (OC) and its three dimensions—affection, continuance, and normative commitment—among Project Managers in an IT consulting firm, providing evidence-based insights for retention strategies and support practices.

Research Procedures

This research will involve the dissemination of an online survey questionnaire that will take approximately 15 to 20 minutes to complete. We have selected you as our research participant because you meet the necessary qualifications for this study: you are currently employed at Seven Seven Global Services, Inc. (77GSI), hold the position of Project Manager, and are currently deployed to a client engagement.

The survey consists of three sections: demographic profile, Perceived Organizational Support (8 items), and Organizational Commitment (18 items). Please note that this is an anonymous survey—no personally identifiable information (such as your name or employee ID) will be collected. Your individual responses will NOT be shared with 77GSI management, HR, or your client counterparts. The collected data will be stored securely in password-protected files accessible only to the researcher, kept for a period until the completion of the study, and then deleted permanently. Results will be presented in aggregate form only (e.g., "70% of Project Managers feel supported..."). No individual respondent will be identified in the final thesis or any publications.

San Beda College Alabang
8 Don Manolo Blvd., Alabang Hills Village,
Muntinlupa City, 1770

Research Ethics Committee Informed Consent Form

Voluntary Participation

Your participation in this study is voluntary, and you are free to leave anytime in case you have accepted the invitation and later on decide to withdraw from this study.

Disclosure of Risks

Your participation in this study does not involve more than minimal risks. While the question may evoke emotions related to your personal experiences, it does not pose any serious psychological harm. In case you need an immediate psychological intervention, you can immediately stop the survey and proceed when you are ready, or we will officially drop the survey.

Benefits

Your participation in this study will help generate evidence-based insights for 77GSI leadership to design better support programs, retention strategies, and engagement initiatives for Project Managers. The findings will identify whether support most strongly influences emotional attachment (affective commitment), perceived costs of leaving (continuance commitment), or felt obligation (normative commitment), allowing the organization to focus interventions effectively. For HR and Organizational Development practitioners, the results can guide training programs and manager capability building, particularly for project managers working in client environments. For delivery leaders and PMO leads, the study provides practical guidance on day-to-day management behaviors that enhance perceived support, such as feedback delivery, escalation management, and resource advocacy. Ultimately, this research contributes to reducing the high attrition rate (22.6%) in the Philippine consulting sector and supports Project Managers in navigating boundary-spanning roles while maintaining strong psychological bonds with the home organization. We will share with you our research results in aggregate form so that you can gain insights into how organizational support influences commitment across your professional peer group at 77GSI.

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Muntinlupa City, 1770

Research Ethics Committee Informed Consent Form

Anonymity and Confidentiality

We will keep your identity with utmost confidentiality. We will not share any information about you outside of our research group and we will use an *alias* to refer to you in our research paper. Rest assured that whatever data obtained from the interview will be properly disposed of and not used in our research.

We thank you for your time, and we hope for your favorable response on this matter. Should you have any questions, please feel free to contact our team at savigorospe@gmail.com or 09219723390.

Sincerely,

2/23/2026
Savipra Alexandrio Gorospe, PMP, Rpm
Principal Researcher

2/23/2026
Dr. Oscar Lacap Jr.
Research Adviser

Appendix B
Approval Form

<p>San Beda College Alabang 8 Don Manolo Blvd., Alabang Hills Village, Muntinlupa City, 1770 RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE</p>			
<p>Approval Form</p>			
Protocol Code:	2026-311	Date of Approval:	Feb. 24, 2026
Research Title:	Perceived Organizational Support and Organizational Commitment: A Predictive Study among Project Managers at 77GSI		
Principal Researcher:	Savipra Alexandrio D. Gorospe		
Degree Program	Master in Business Administration		

The following documents (//) have been submitted and reviewed in connection with the above study by the researchers for ethics review:

- (/) Research Proposal
- (/) Informed Consent/Assent Forms
- (/) Curriculum Vitae
- (/) Data Collection Tools
- (/) Others, please specify: Permission letter to the original source of the questionnaire.

The Research Ethics Committee hereby approve to:

- () proceed to instrument validation
- (/) proceed to data collection, organization and write up

<p>Remarks</p> <p>Proceed to data gathering.</p>

Approved by:

Levie G. Santos, MBA, LPT
 Chair, Research Ethics Committee
 San Beda College Alabang

REC-B05

Appendix C
Letter of Permission for Research Instrument: SPOS

San Beda College Alabang
8 Don Manolo Blvd., Alabang Hills Village,
Muntinlupa City, 1770

OFFICE OF THE GRADUATE SCHOOL

February 23, 2026

Department of Psychology
University of Delaware
Newark, DE 19716
Subject: Notification of SPOS Use for MBA Thesis Research
Email: psych-dept@udel.edu

Subject: Notification of SPOS Use for MBA Thesis Research

Dear Department Chair,

I am writing to notify your department of my intent to use the Survey of Perceived Organizational Support (SPOS), originally developed by Dr. Robert Eisenberger and colleagues (1986), in my MBA thesis at San Beda College Alabang, Philippines.

- Study: Perceived Organizational Support and Organizational Commitment among Project Managers (Protocol 2026-311)
- Instrument: 8-item SPOS short form
- Use: Anonymous online survey of 80 Project Managers

I understand the SPOS is freely available for academic research and Dr. Eisenberger intended it to be accessible without licensing restrictions. I will ensure proper citation of the original source.

This notification is submitted to comply with our Research Ethics Committee requirements. Please confirm receipt or advise if there are any concerns.

Thank you.

Respectfully,

 2/23/2026
Savipra Alexandrie D. Gorospe, PMP, RPm
MBA Candidate
2024500008@sanbeda-alabang.edu.ph

Appendix D
Letter of Permission for Research Instrument: TCM

 San Beda College Alabang
8 Don Manolo Blvd., Alabang Hills Village,
Muntinlupa City, 1770

 OFFICE OF THE GRADUATE SCHOOL

February 23, 2026

To: Dr. John P. Meyer
Industrial and Organizational Psychology Research Group
Department of Psychology
Western University
London, Ontario N6A 5C2, Canada
Email: info@employeecommitment.com; meyer@uwo.ca

Subject: Academic License Confirmation for TCM Employee Commitment Survey

I am writing as a courtesy to inform you of my use of the TCM Employee Commitment Survey in my MBA thesis research at San Beda College Alabang.

For your records:

- Study: Perceived Organizational Support and Organizational Commitment: A Predictive Study among Project Managers at 77GSI
- REC Protocol: 2026-311
- Institution: San Beda College Alabang, Graduate School
- Academic License: Previously obtained on November 16, 2025 (confirmation email attached for reference)

I have already downloaded and agreed to the terms of the Academic License for the TCM Employee Commitment Survey through employeecommitment.com. This letter is submitted as a courtesy notification to satisfy our Research Ethics Committee's requirement for documented correspondence with instrument authors.

I confirm continued compliance with all academic license terms:

- Single research project use (thesis only)
- No commercial application or client billing
- Proper citation of Meyer & Allen (1997) and Meyer, Allen, & Smith (1993)
- Anonymous data collection with secure storage

Thank you for providing this validated instrument to academic researchers. Please confirm receipt of this courtesy notification.

Respectfully,

 2/23/2026
Savipra Alexantrio D. Gorospe, PMP, RPm
MBA Candidate
2024500008@sanbeda-alabang.edu.ph
Attachment: Academic License Confirmation Email (November 16, 2025)

TCM Employee Commitment Survey | Academic Download

info@employeecommitment.com via server.worlddiscoveries.co

To: Savipra Alexandrio D. Gorospe Sun 11/16/2025 2:17 PM

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TCM Employee Commitment Survey | Academic Download

Name: Savipra Alexandrio Gorospe
Email: 2024500008@sanbeda-alabang.edu.ph

To download a copy of the **TCM** Employee Commitment Survey - Academic Package, please click the following link: <http://employeecommitment.com/TCM-Employee-Commitment-Survey-Academic-Package-2004.pdf>

This email and any files transmitted with it are confidential and intended solely for the use of the individual or entity to whom they are addressed. If you have received this email in error please discard and notify the sender.

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Appendix E
Request for Permission to Conduct Thesis Research

 San Beda College Alabang
8 Don Manolo Blvd., Alabang Hills Village,
Muntinlupa City, 1770

 OFFICE OF THE GRADUATE SCHOOL

February 11, 2025

Ms. Meg Hernandez
PMO Manager
Seven Seven Global Services, Inc. (77GSI)
The Orient Square, F. Ortigas Jr. Rd,
San Antonio, Ortigas Center,
Pasig City, Metro Manila, Philippines

Dear Ms. Hernandez,

Subject: Request for Permission to Conduct Thesis Research

I am writing to formally request permission to conduct a research study at Seven Seven Global Services, Inc. (77GSI) as part of the requirements for my Master of Business Administration (MBA) degree at San Beda College Alabang. I am a graduate student under the supervision of John Castillo, and my research focuses on understanding the factors that influence employee commitment in IT consulting firms.

The title of my thesis is:

"Perceived Organizational Support as a Predictor of Organizational Commitment among Project Managers at Seven Seven Global Services, Inc. (77GSI)."

The primary objective of this study is to examine how perceived organizational support (POS) predicts the three components of organizational commitment— affective, continuance, and normative— among project managers at 77GSI. This research will employ a quantitative predictive design using standardized survey instruments, specifically the Survey of Perceived Organizational Support (SPOS) and the Three-Component Model Employee Commitment Survey. Data collection will involve approximately 100 project managers currently employed at 77GSI, and participation will be entirely voluntary and confidential.

Benefits to Seven Seven Global Services, Inc.

This research presents several valuable benefits to 77GSI:

- Enhanced Understanding of Employee Commitment Drivers:** The study will provide 77GSI with data-driven insights into how project managers perceive organizational support and how these perceptions influence their commitment to the company. This understanding is particularly valuable in the consulting industry where project managers operate in dual organizational environments— serving client needs while maintaining allegiance to the parent organization.

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Muntinlupa City, 1770

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2. Evidence-Based Recommendations for HR Practices: The findings will offer actionable recommendations for enhancing human resource management practices, including strategies to strengthen perceived organizational support among project managers. This can inform the development of support systems, communication practices, and recognition programs that are particularly relevant for project managers working in boundary-spanning roles.

3. Improved Employee Retention Strategies: By identifying the specific dimensions of commitment (affective, continuance, normative) that are most strongly predicted by perceived organizational support, 77GSI can tailor its retention strategies more effectively. This is especially important in the competitive consulting industry where skilled project managers are valuable assets whose retention is critical for organizational success.

4. Cultural Context Insights: As a Filipino organization operating in the global marketplace, 77GSI embodies the intersection of local cultural values and international business practices. This study will provide insights into how Filipino cultural values—such as *utang na loob* (debt of gratitude), *hiya* (social propriety), and *pakikisama* (smooth interpersonal relationships)—shape the relationship between organizational support and commitment. These culturally-specific findings can inform more effective management approaches that resonate with Filipino employees.

5. Benchmarking and Best Practices: The research will position 77GSI within the broader landscape of IT consulting firms in the Philippines and Asia. The findings can serve as a benchmark for comparing 77GSI's organizational support and commitment levels against industry standards, identifying areas of strength and opportunities for improvement.

6. Academic-Industry Collaboration: Participation in this study demonstrates 77GSI's commitment to evidence-based management and continuous improvement. Upon completion, I will be pleased to share a summary of the research findings with your organization, providing you with valuable insights at no cost.

Assurance of Confidentiality and Ethical Standards

I assure you that this research will adhere to the highest ethical standards. All data collected will be treated with strict confidentiality, and no individual responses will be identifiable in the final report. Participation will be entirely voluntary, and participants may withdraw at any time without penalty. The study will be subject to the review of Research and Ethics Committee (REC) of San Beda College Alabang to ensure compliance with ethical research guidelines.

The data collection process will be designed to minimize disruption to normal operations. Participants will complete an online survey that takes approximately 15-20 minutes to finish. I am

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Muntinlupa City, 1770

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happy to coordinate with your office to schedule the data collection at a time that is most convenient for your organization.

I sincerely hope that you will grant permission for this research to be conducted at 77GSI. Your support will not only contribute to the completion of my MBA degree but will also provide your organization with valuable insights that can enhance employee commitment and organizational effectiveness.

Should you have any questions or require additional information, please do not hesitate to contact me at 2024500008@sanbeda-alabang.edu.ph or 0921-972-3390. I would be grateful for the opportunity to discuss this proposal with you in person at your earliest convenience.

Thank you for considering this request. I look forward to your favorable response.

Respectfully yours,

Savipra Alexandrio D. Gorospe, PMP
MBA Candidate
San Beda College Alabang
savipragorospe@outlook.com
+63-921-972-3390

Appendix F
Survey of Perceived Organizational Support (SPOS)

INSTRUCTIONS: Please indicate the degree of your agreement with each of the following statements regarding 77 Global Services Inc. (Your Employer).

1 – Strongly Disagree; 2 – Moderately Disagree; 3 – Slightly Disagree;

4 – Neither Agree nor Disagree; 5 – Slightly Agree; 6 – Moderately Agree; 7 – Strongly Agree

Indicators	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
The organization values my contribution to its well-being.							
If the organization could hire someone to replace me at a lower salary it would do so. (Reverse Scored)							
The organization fails to appreciate any extra effort from me. (Reverse Scored)							
The organization strongly considers my goals and values.							
The organization would ignore any complaint from me. (Reverse Scored)							
The organization disregards my best interests when it makes decisions that affect me. (Reverse Scored)							
Help is available from the organization when I have a problem.							
The organization really cares about my well-being.							

Overview of Instruments Validity

The study utilizes two primary, internationally validated instruments to measure the relationship between **Perceived Organizational Support (POS)** and **Organizational Commitment (OC)**. These instruments are selected for their established psychometric properties and their relevance to the project management context in the Philippines.

1. Survey of Perceived Organizational Support (SPOS)

The construct of POS is measured using the **8-item short version** of the instrument originally developed by *Eisenberger et al. (1986)*.

Construct Nature

POS is treated as a unidimensional construct representing the global belief that the organization values an employee's contributions and cares about their well-being.

Reliability Data

The short-form version is utilized to minimize respondent fatigue while maintaining high internal consistency. Prior empirical studies have reported Cronbach's alpha coefficients exceeding the **.90 benchmark**.

Scoring

Items are assessed using a **7-point Likert scale**, ranging from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree," and include reverse-scored items to ensure response quality.

Appendix G
Three Component Model (TCM)

INSTRUCTIONS: Put a (✓) mark on the box beside your selected answer that will accurately represent the level of your agreeableness on each item.

1 – Strongly Disagree; 2 – Disagree; 3 – Slightly Disagree;

4 – Undecided; 5 – Slightly Agree; 6 – Agree; 7 – Strongly Agree

Indicators	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Affective Commitment							
I would be very happy to spend the rest of my career with this organization.							
I really feel as if this organization's problems are my own.							
I do not feel a strong sense of "belonging" to my organization.							
I do not feel "emotionally attached" to this organization.							
I do not feel like "part of the family" at my organization.							
This organization has a great deal of personal meaning for me.							
Continuance Commitment							
Right now, staying with my organization is a matter of necessity as much as desire.							
It would be very hard for me to leave my organization right now, even if I wanted to.							
Too much of my life would be disrupted if I decided I wanted to leave my organization now.							
I feel that I have too few options to consider leaving this organization.							
If I had not already put so much of myself into this organization, I might consider working elsewhere.							
One of the few negative consequences of leaving this organization would be the scarcity of available alternatives.							
Normative Commitment							
I do not feel any obligation to remain with my current employer.							
Even if it were to my advantage, I do not feel it would be right to leave my organization now.							
I would feel guilty if I left my organization now.							
This organization deserves my loyalty.							
I would not leave my organization right now because I have a sense of obligation to the people in it.							
I owe a great deal to my organization.							

2. Three-Component Model (TCM) of Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment is operationalized through the **Three-Component Model** developed by *Meyer and Allen (1991, 1997)*.

Dimensions

The instrument consists of **18 items** divided into three distinct subscales:

- **Affective Commitment:** Emotional attachment and identification with the organization.
- **Continuance Commitment:** Perceived costs and necessity associated with leaving the organization.
- **Normative Commitment:** Felt moral or relational obligation to remain with the employer.

Reliability Data

Previous psychometric evaluations of these scales have reported strong Cronbach's alpha coefficients:

Commitment Dimension	Cronbach's Alpha
Affective Commitment	.85
Continuance Commitment	.79
Normative Commitment	.73

Instrument Validation Protocol

To ensure the instruments remain reliable within the specific context of 77GSI project managers, the following steps will be taken:

1. **Contextual Referencing:** Items are specifically phrased to refer to "the organization" as the parent consulting firm (77GSI) to distinguish it from the client-site environment.
2. **Internal Consistency Check** Upon completion of data collection, the researcher will compute the Cronbach's alpha for the 77GSI dataset to confirm that the reliability of the POS and OC scales meets the required behavioral research standards in the current sample.

Appendix H Token of Appreciation Notification

Research Proposal: Insights on PM Retention and Organizational Support for 77GSI 2 messages

From: "Savipra Alexandrio Gorospe" <sgorospe@77global.biz> February 23, 2026 11:34 PM

To: "mauricebenedictob@77global.biz" <mauricebenedictob@77global.biz>

Cc: "2024500008" <2024500008@sanbeda-alabang.edu.ph> "savipragorospe" <savipragorospe@outlook.com>

Dear Meg and Maureen,

Good day. I hope this message finds you both well.

I am writing to express my sincere gratitude for your support and approval of my MBA thesis research at 77GSI, "Perceived Organizational Support and Organizational Commitment among Project Managers." Your endorsement has been instrumental in allowing me to proceed with this study.

Upon completion of data collection, I would like to present you with a token of appreciation for your generosity in facilitating this research. Additionally, I commit to sharing the aggregate findings and executive summary with you once the study is completed, hopefully providing valuable insights for our retention and support initiatives.

Thank you again for your trust and support in this academic endeavor.
Respectfully,

Savipra Alexandrio D. Gorospe
Senior Project Manager, 77GSI
MBA Candidate, San Beda College Alabang
Email: 2024500008@sanbeda-alabang.edu.ph
Mobile: +63-921-972-3390

Appendix I
Statistical Analysis

Descriptives

Descriptives

	N	Mean	SD	Minimum	Maximum
POS_Mean	75	5.26	1.012	2.88	7.00
Affective_Mean	75	4.72	0.987	2.33	7.00
Continuance_Mean	75	4.85	1.285	1.67	7.00
Normative_Mean	75	5.02	1.251	1.50	7.00
OC_Overall	75	4.87	0.892	2.67	6.67

Descriptives

	Mean	SD
POS_1	5.55	1.24
POS_2_R	4.47	1.77
POS_3_R	5.11	1.33
POS_4	5.17	1.32
POS_5_R	5.35	1.27
POS_6_R	5.08	1.52
POS_7	5.83	1.03
POS_8	5.56	1.11

Descriptives

	Mean	SD
AFF_1	4.79	1.51
AFF_2	4.45	1.39
AFF_3_R	4.73	1.34
AFF_4_R	4.45	1.47
AFF_5_R	4.83	1.28
AFF_6	5.09	1.18

Descriptives

	Mean	SD
CONT_1	5.57	1.40
CONT_2	4.97	1.53
CONT_3	4.96	1.76
CONT_4	4.64	1.71
CONT_5	4.09	1.61
CONT_6	4.88	1.67

Descriptives

	Mean	SD
NORM_1_R	4.71	1.58
NORM_2	4.91	1.57
NORM_3	4.93	1.59
NORM_4	5.07	1.66
NORM_5	5.19	1.39
NORM_6	5.32	1.64

Linear Regression - POS and OC

Model Fit Measures

Model	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Overall Model Test			
			F	df1	df2	p
1	0.461	0.453	62.4	1	73	< .001

Note. Models estimated using sample size of N=75

Model Coefficients - OC_Overall

Predictor	Estimate	SE	95% Confidence Interval		t	p
			Lower	Upper		
Intercept	1.718	0.4059	0.909	2.527	4.23	< .001
POS_Mean	0.598	0.0757	0.447	0.749	7.90	< .001

Linear Regression - POS and AC

Model Fit Measures

Model	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Overall Model Test			
			F	df1	df2	p
1	0.424	0.416	53.7	1	73	< .001

Note. Models estimated using sample size of N=75

Model Coefficients - Affective_Mean

Predictor	Estimate	SE	95% Confidence Interval		t	p
			Lower	Upper		
Intercept	1.385	0.4640	0.460	2.310	2.99	0.004
POS_Mean	0.634	0.0866	0.462	0.807	7.33	< .001

Linear Regression - POS and CC

Model Fit Measures

Model	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Overall Model Test			
			F	df1	df2	p
1	0.0895	0.0771	7.18	1	73	0.009

Note. Models estimated using sample size of N=75

Model Coefficients - Continuance_Mean

Predictor	Estimate	SE	95% Confidence Interval		t	p
			Lower	Upper		
Intercept	2.855	0.759	1.3414	4.368	3.76	< .001
POS_Mean	0.380	0.142	0.0973	0.662	2.68	0.009

Linear Regression - POS and NC

Model Fit Measures

Model	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Overall Model Test			
			F	df1	df2	p
1	0.399	0.391	48.4	1	73	< .001

Note. Models estimated using sample size of N=75

Model Coefficients - Normative_Mean

Predictor	Estimate	SE	95% Confidence Interval		t	p
			Lower	Upper		
Intercept	0.913	0.601	-0.284	2.11	1.52	0.133
POS_Mean	0.780	0.112	0.557	1.00	6.96	< .001

Appendix J Assumption Checks

Assessment of Regression Assumptions

Prior to interpretation of the regression results, the three key assumptions of simple linear regression, namely, linearity, normality of the residuals and homoscedasticity, were checked for each of the four models in accordance with the statistical treatment plan outlined in Chapter 3. The diagnostic procedures selected were visual inspection of scatterplots, residuals versus fitted plots, normal Q-Q plots, and the normal Q-Q plot, and Shapiro-Wilk test for normality of residuals.

Linearity

Linearity was examined by analyzing bivariate scatterplots of POS against each outcome variable of OC, with regression line superimposed on the scatterplot. These scatterplots are given for all four models in Figure 2. As you can see in each panel below, the data points are spread in a roughly linear fashion about the regression line and there is no obvious curve or systematic bending. The linear model is therefore suitable for four relationships.

Figure J1

Scatterplots of POS Against Each Organizational Commitment Outcome (N = 75)

Note. Each panel displays the bivariate scatterplot of Perceived Organizational Support (POS) against the respective commitment outcome. The red line represents the fitted simple linear regression line. Pearson correlation coefficients are shown in each panel.

Normality of Residuals

The results in the normality of the residuals were examined using two complementary approaches: (a) using the Shapiro-Wilk test applied to the model residuals for each regression model, and (b) the visual inspection of normal Q-Q plots. The results

of the Shapiro-Wilk test are shown in Table 10, while the Q-Q plots are shown in Figure 3.

Table J1

Shapiro–Wilk Test of Normality for Regression Residuals (N = 75)

Model	Shapiro–Wilk W	p
POS → Overall OC	.970	.070
POS → Affective Commitment	.982	.379
POS → Continuance Commitment	.972	.098
POS → Normative Commitment	.965	.037*

Note. Non-significant p-values indicate that residuals do not significantly deviate from normality. * $p < .05$.

Three of the four models met the assumption of normality at $\alpha = .05$: Residuals for POS - Overall OC ($W = .970, p = .070$), POS - Affective Commitment ($W = .982, p = .379$), and POS - Continuance Commitment ($W = .972, p = .098$) were not statistically different from a normal distribution. For the POS - Normative Commitment model, the Shapiro-Wilk test produced a slightly significant result ($W = .965, p = .037$), which means there is a slight deviation from normality in the residuals. However, simple linear regression has been known to be relatively robust in the face of minor violations of normality, especially as sample sizes are approaching or larger than 75 (Field, 2018; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2019). Visual inspection of the corresponding Q-Q plot (Figure 3, bottom-right panel) shows that the deviation is very small: the data points follow the reference line quite closely, with slight deviations from it at the tails. Given this, the results of this regression for the Normative Commitment model are interpretable and valid.

Figure J2

Normal Q–Q Plots of Residuals for Each Regression Model (N = 75)

Note. Each panel displays the normal Q–Q plot of regression residuals for the respective model. Points falling along the red reference line indicate normally distributed residuals. Minor departures at the tails are acceptable for regression analysis.

Homoscedasticity

Another diagnostic is the Homoscedasticity, which is the assumption of constant variance of residuals for all the fitted values -- was assessed by visual inspection of the residuals vs. fitted values plots. These plots for all four models are presented in Figure 4. In each panel, the residuals are scattered around the horizontal zero line randomly, with

That in all things, God may be glorified

no systematic fanning, funnel shape or patterned clustering of the residuals. The spread of residuals seems to be roughly constant over the range of fitted values for all the four models, thereby confirming the homoscedasticity assumption.

Figure J3

Residuals vs. Fitted Values Plots for Each Regression Model (N = 75)

Note. Each panel displays the residuals plotted against the fitted values for the respective regression model. The dashed red line marks zero residual. Random scatter around the line with no systematic pattern indicates that the homoscedasticity assumption is met.

Summary of Assumption Checks

The assumptions of linearity and homoscedasticity were met completely in all four models of regression. The normality assumption was satisfied for three of the four models; the Normative Commitment model had a slight departure ($W = .965$, $p = .037$) that visual inspection of the Q-Q plot proved to be minor and non-consequential. Accordingly, where regression results are displayed for all four models, they are interpreted with confidence keeping a short note of caution here for the Normative Commitment model where appropriate.

Appendix K

Usage of AI Tools

In line with the ethical framework of AI-assisted academic writing suggested by Cheng et al. (2025), the three AI tools were used when preparing this manuscript: Google NotebookLM, Grammarly, and Claude. This appendix has a detailed description of each tool, such as the description of the tool, the method of its use, and the reason why it was used, and then a description of the originality checking methods, which were used before making final submissions. Tier 1 (ethically acceptable) and Tier 2 (ethically contingent) tasks as outlined by Cheng et al. (2025) were limited to all AI-assisted activities. Any Tier 3 activity such as drafting de novo text, creating new ideas, analyzing study data, literature review, or reference creation was done without an AI tool.

Tool 1: Google NotebookLM

Description of the Tool

Google NotebookLM is an AI-based research assistant created by Google LLC. NotebookLM is document-anchored, unlike general-purpose large language models that use public internet data: it only works on files uploaded by the user and does not generate content out-of-band. This design is especially appropriate to Tier 2 tasks - summarizing and making sense of pre-existing content presented by the researcher - with least risks of hallucination and fabricated references recognized by Cheng et al. (2025).

How the Tool was Used

The main reference materials of the study were placed in Google NotebookLM as a centralized repository of documents. The PDFs uploaded into the researcher NotebookLM workspace and consulted during the process of writing the manuscript included (a) journal articles and empirical studies, which made up the Review of Related Literature (RRL); (b) Statistical Power Analysis of Behavioral Sciences (Cohen, 1988); (c)

the texts of Creswell on the research methodology; (d) the publication manual of the American Psychological Association (7th ed.); (e) the Journal Article Reporting Standards for Quantitative Research in Psychology (JARS-QUANT; APA, 2020); and (f) JAMOVI user documentation and statistical instructions. The researcher used NotebookLM to search these uploaded files to identify certain sections, definitions, and statistical criteria in the files - it is not a content generator but a library of searchable and AI-assisted references.

Why the Tool was Used

The main reason why NotebookLM was used was due to its practical efficiency: the size and technical complexity of the reference materials used in five chapters made it time-consuming to navigate the documents. NotebookLM allowed the researcher to find the passages, statistical thresholds, and methodological criteria that were relevant to the research more easily by consolidating all reference PDFs into one, query-able workspace without delegating any intellectual or analytical work to the software. This application is in Tier 2 of the Cheng et al. (2025) framework - namely, summarizing content - because the tool rearranged and revealed information previously written or found by the researcher, and the researcher checked all the information retrieved in the original source documents before using it.

Tool 2: Grammarly

Description of the Tool

The Grammarly Inc. has developed an AI-based writing assistant called Grammar. It is a browser extension and desktop app that offers real-time grammar correction, spelling verification, readability rating, sentence-level style and flow recommendations. As mentioned by Cheng et al. (2025), Grammarly was specifically found as a purposely built

AI writing assistant that is optimized to Tier 1 tasks - grammar and spelling correction, and readability improvement - and that such tools are adapted to perform such functions specifically because they are designed to do so.

How the Tool was Used

Grammarly was used throughout the drafting and revision stages of the manuscript to improve the legibility and paragraph flow of researcher-written text. Specific applications included: (a) correcting grammatical errors, punctuation inconsistencies, and spelling mistakes in researcher-drafted paragraphs; (b) receiving suggestions for restructuring sentences that were identified as overly long, fragmented, or difficult to follow; and (c) reviewing overall paragraph cohesion and transition quality between ideas. All Grammarly suggestions were reviewed individually by the researcher; no suggestion was applied automatically or without deliberate consideration of whether it preserved the intended meaning and voice of the passage. Samples of Grammarly's revision suggestions, alongside the researcher's final accepted edits, are documented as exhibit screenshots included in this appendix see Figure L1.

Figure K1

Sample Grammarly Paragraph Selector with Improve, Rephrase, and Revise Tone

Why the Tool was Used

Being a non-native English academic writer in a technically challenging field, the researcher used Grammarly to make sure that the passages of manuscripts were of the precise grammatical correctness and readability that the graduate level academic writing is supposed to have, without losing the analytical voice and thought of the researcher. Cheng et al. (2025) categorize this type of use as Tier 1 (ethically acceptable), as long as all AI-made edits are verified to be in their own voice and with a critical mindset (a requirement that was followed throughout the research paper in this study).

Tool 2: Claude

Description of the Tool

Claude is a Large Language Model (LLM) developed by Anthropic. The version accessed during the preparation of this manuscript was Claude Sonnet, available through

the Claude.ai web interface. Claude is a general-purpose AI assistant capable of explaining and clarifying difficult information into a more easily comprehensible form.

How the Tool was Used

Claude was used for one primary purpose: to generate structured statistical benchmark reference cards for use during the statistical review and preparation for the oral defense presentation. These reference cards were compiled from thresholds and indicators from statistical authorities already identified and verified by the researcher, specifically effect size benchmarks from Cohen (1988); correlation strength benchmarks from Evans (1996); and regression and normality testing benchmarks from Field (2018) and Tabachnick & Fidell (2019). The researcher provided the source, criterion, and corresponding threshold values; Claude organized and formatted these into a structured, tabular reference card layout that the researcher used in the oral defense presentation slides as shown in Figure L2.

Figure K2

Statistical Benchmark Reference Card generated by Claude

Statistical Benchmarks Reference Card			
Gorospe (2026) — POS & OC Predictive Study, San Beda College Alabang For oral defense preparation			
1 Descriptive statistics — mean interpretation (7-point Likert scale) Sevitta et al. (1992); Likert (1932)			
Range	Verbal description	Your study values	
1.00 – 1.99	Strongly disagree / Very low	—	
2.00 – 3.99	Disagree / Low → Moderately low	—	
4.00 – 4.59	Neither agree nor disagree / Moderate	AC = 4.72 ← borders this zone	
4.60 – 5.39	Slightly agree / Moderately high	POS=5.26, OC=4.87, CC=4.85, NC=5.02	
5.40 – 6.19	Agree / High	—	
6.20 – 7.00	Strongly agree / Very high	—	
Interval size = $(7 - 1) / 7 = 0.857$. Equal-Interval method standard in Philippine graduate research. "Moderate to moderately-high" label applies to scores in the 4.60–5.39 band, below the 5.40 threshold for High.			
2 Reliability — Cronbach's alpha (α) classification George & Mallery (2003); Nunnally (1978)			
α value	Interpretation	Your scales	
α > .90	Excellent	—	
.80 < α ≤ .90	Good	SPOS=.802 CC=.883 NC=.883 OC=.887	
.70 < α ≤ .80	Acceptable	AC = .817	
.60 < α ≤ .70	Questionable	—	
.50 < α ≤ .60	Poor	—	
α ≤ .50	Unacceptable	—	
Nunnally (1978) sets the minimum at .70 (Psychometric Theory). George & Mallery (2003) SPSS for Windows Step by Step provides the full graded classification above. All scales pass — SPOS/CC/NC/OC are 'Good'; AC is 'Acceptable'.			
3 Correlation — Pearson r effect size interpretation Cohen (1988); Evans (1996)			
r range	Cohen (1988)	Evans (1996)	Your correlations
.00 – .09	—	Negligible	—
.10 – .19	Small	Very weak	AC-CC = .100
.20 – .29	Small	Weak	—
.30 – .39	Medium	Weak	POS-CC = .200
.40 – .59	Medium	Moderate	—
.60 – .79	Large	Strong	POS-AC=.651 POS-NC=.631 POS-OC=.670
.80 – 1.00	Large	Very strong	NC-OC = .871
Cohen (1988) Statistical Power Analysis for the Behavioral Sciences (2nd ed.); small r=.10, medium r=.30, large r=.50. Evans (1996) Straightforward Statistics for the Behavioral Sciences provides finer splits commonly cited in Philippine research.			
4 Regression assumptions — decision rules Field (2018); Tabachnick & Fidell (2019)			
Assumption	Method	Decision rule	Your result
Linearity	Bivariate scatterplot + regression line	No systematic curve or bend in scatter pattern	Met — all 4 models
Normality of residuals	Shapiro-Wilk test + Q-Q plot (dual method)	S-W: p > .05 = normality met; Q-Q: points track reference line	Met — 3 of 4 models NC: W=.965, p=.037 (minor)
Homoscedasticity	Residuals vs. fitted values plot	Random scatter around zero line; no funnel or fan shape	Met — all 4 models
NC normally violation defense: Field (2018) Discovering Statistics (5th ed.) and Tabachnick & Fidell (2019) Using Multivariate Statistics (7th ed.) both state that at N ≥ 75, the Central Limit Theorem renders minor residual non-normality non-consequential. Shapiro-Wilk becomes overly sensitive at larger N.			
5 Regression effect size — R² interpretation (Cohen's benchmarks) Cohen (1988); Cohen et al. (2003)			
R ² value	Effect size	Cohen's f ²	Your models
R ² = .02	Small	f ² = .02	—
R ² = .13	Medium	f ² = .15	CC = .090 (between Small & Medium; p = .000, real effect)

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Originality Verification and AI Detection

Tools and Procedures Used

Before final submission, originality and textual resemblance of the manuscript were checked with Turnitin, which is a standard plagiarism checking service used by San Beda College Alabang in reviewing graduate theses. The verification process was carried out under the oversight of the thesis professor, to whom the researcher sent the manuscript in two versions, (a) each chapter separately (Chapters 1 to 5) was sent separately to enable similarities check at a chapter level; and (b) the entire, consolidated manuscript was sent as one document to enable an overall originality check. The thesis professor reviewed Turnitin Similarity Reports and any flagged passages that needed to be revised were handled by the researcher prior to the final version being delivered to the panel.

The researcher admits that the traditional plagiarism detection tools, such as Turnitin, are not specifically developed to identify AI-generated text. Nevertheless, the main protection that was implemented in this research was the intentional confinement of the use of AI tools to Tier 1 and Tier 2, so that no massive amount of text was produced by any AI tool. Manuscript content was authored by the researcher and AI tools were only applied to enhance grammar and readability (Grammarly), find and structure reference materials (NotebookLM), and present the reference material provided by the researcher as structured reference cards (Claude). Based on this, the researcher confirms that the four-question Author Checklist of Ethical Use of Generative AI Tools as suggested by Cheng et al. (2025) has been followed: (a) all major ideas, insights, interpretations, and critical analyses belong to the researcher; (b) the researcher used human competency in core research and writing skills throughout the research; (c) all content and reference

entries were independently verified by the researcher for accuracy and reliability; and (d) the use of AI tools is disclosed fully and transparently in this appendix and in the Data Gathering Procedures section of Chapter 3.

Appendix L
Certification from Grammarian

San Beda College Alabang
8 Don Manolo Blvd., Alabang Hills Village,
Muntinlupa City, 1770

SCHOOL OF BUSINESS, ACCOUNTANCY, AND MANAGEMENT
Master in Business Administration (MBA)

GRAMMARIAN'S CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that the undersigned has reviewed and gone through all the pages of the study manuscript entitled: **"Perceived Organizational Support and Organizational Commitment: A Predictive Study among Project Managers at 77GSI"**, written by Savipra Alexandrio D. Gorospe.

The paper has been aligned with the set of structural rules governing the composition of sentences, phrases, and words in the English Language.

Certification Issued by:

Name: Julie Ann E. Dela Rosa, LPT

Profession/Designation: Grammarian

PRC No.: 1516366

Date Signed: April 25, 2026

Julie Ann E. Dela Rosa, LPT

Teacher - Applicant

Passionate teacher committed to inspiring learners, building confidence, and creating meaningful, student-centered experiences

0926-0838-725

plukjulieannndelarosa@gmail.com

0826 Uban, Catmon,
Santa Maria, Bulacan

SKILLS

- * Literary & Creative Skills
- * Editing & Language Skills
- * Design & Layout Skills
- * Communication & Coaching Skills
- * Adaptability & Collaboration
- * Events Management

EXPERIENCE

Liceo di San Lorenzo

Teacher

2016-2019

TaskUs

Customer Service Representative

2019-2022

Sta. Maria National High School

Teacher II

2022-
PRESENT

ACHIEVEMENTS

- * AWARD-WINNING COACH
 - Journalism
 - BULPRISA Cultural Events
- * AWARD - WINNING TEACHER
 - Spoken Poetry
 - Talumpating Di-Handa
- * School Researcher

EDUCATION

Polytechnic University of the Philippines

Bachelor in Secondary Education major in English
Cum Laude

Student Council Officer 2014-2016

2012-2016

St. Joseph College of Bulacan

San Jose Patag, Santa Maria Bulacan
5th Honorable Mention

2012-2016

Pila Elementary School

Pila, Catmon, Santa Maria Bulacan
Class Valedictorian
SSLG Governor

2001-2012

CHARACTER REFERENCE

Cecille T. Pascual, LPT

0942-9357-825

Annabelle C. Del Rosario, LPT, Rpm, RPsy, PhD.

0917-5857-825

Republic of the Philippines
PROFESSIONAL REGULATION COMMISSION
PROFESSIONAL IDENTIFICATION CARD

LAST NAME ▶ DELA ROSA
 FIRST NAME ▶ JULIE ANN
 MIDDLE NAME ▶ ELECHICON
 REGISTRATION NO. ▶ 1516366
 REGISTRATION DATE ▶ 12/27/2016
 VALID UNTIL ▶ 03/13/2028

PROFESSIONAL TEACHER

Professional Regulation Commission
www.prc.gov.ph

CERTIFICATION

24-8110010 This is to certify that the person whose name, photograph, and signature appear herein is a duly registered professional, legally authorized to practice his/her profession with all the rights and privileges appurtenant thereto.

This is to certify further that he/she is a professional in good standing and that his/her certificate of registration/professional license has not been suspended, revoked or withdrawn.

 Signature of Professional

CHARITO A. ZAMORA
 Chairperson

Appendix M
Curriculum Vitae

Savipra Alexandrio D. Gorospe, PMP, CLSSYB

BF International, Las Piñas City 1740 | [LinkedIn](#) | [Jobstreet](#) | 0921-972-3390 | savigorospe@gmail.com

PROFESSIONAL SUMMARY

Senior Project Manager with 7+ years of experience leading enterprise projects and digital transformation initiatives across HCM SaaS, Pharma, Aviation, and Banking, supported by 11 years of overall professional experience including BPM operations. Adept in Predictive, Adaptive, and Hybrid project development approaches, utilizing expertise in PMO Governance and tailoring processes for SDLC compliance and audit-ready Control Gates design. Proven success in governing a high-volume portfolio (180+ initiatives), collectively generating \$1M+ in business value, by driving formalized Risk assessment and ensuring the delivery of strategic project outcomes. Certified PMP, CAPM, CLSSYB, and Agile Professional, demonstrating core competence in the Stakeholders Performance Domain and Accountable Leadership. Currently pursuing an MBA to strengthen strategic and executive capabilities.

WORK EXPERIENCE

Seven Seven Global Services, Inc. (77GSD) – BDO Unibank, Inc. **Pasig City, NCR, Philippines**
Senior Project Manager *April 2025 – Present*

- **Project Life Cycle Management:** Orchestrated end-to-end delivery using Predictive (plan-driven) approaches, diligently managing the Scope, Schedule, and Finance Performance Domains to maintain the integrated baseline and ensure on-time, on-budget project completion.
- **Integrated Governance & Oversight:** Strengthened the Governance Performance Domain by establishing project-level processes and metrics, delivering Work Performance Reports and dashboards to provide strategic oversight and align with the Adopt a Holistic View principle.
- **Risk & Change Management:** Proactively managed the Risk Performance Domain by performing comprehensive assessments, analyzing impacts on dependencies, and implementing mitigation strategies in the Monitoring and Controlling Focus Area.
- **Quality & Compliance (Closing Focus Area):** Elevated organizational maturity by designing and implementing Control Gate readiness checklists for critical UAT-to-PROD transitions, embedding Quality into Processes and Deliverables to ensure audit-ready releases.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Led cross-functional collaboration (Business, Technology, Operations) to clarify requirements (Elicit and Analyze Requirements), secure executive approvals, and facilitate optimal Stakeholder alignment across the project life cycle.

Ascendion (formerly Collabera Digital) – Cebu Pacific **Makati City, NCR, Philippines**
Project Manager / Scrum Master *August 2024 – Present*

- **Adaptive Delivery Leadership:** Led execution for mobile development projects utilizing Hybrid Development Approaches, serving as a servant leader to manage Adaptive increments (Scrum Master functions) and overseeing Predictive elements (release management).
- **Scope & Value Optimization:** Optimized the Scope Performance Domain by maintaining and prioritizing the Product Backlog (Artifact) through continuous Backlog Refinement, ensuring feature development prioritized Business Value and alignment with the overall product roadmap.

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- **Performance Measurement:** Tracked team efficiency and productivity using adaptive Tools and Techniques such as velocity, Burndown Charts, and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) documented within Azure DevOps.
- **Continuous Improvement:** Drove process optimization and systematically captured Lessons Learned in the Manage Project Knowledge process to enhance workflow efficiencies and continually refine project Governance frameworks.
- **Resources and Culture:** Managed the Resources Performance Domain by planning capacity, allocating personnel, and coaching the cross-functional team, fostering an Empowered Culture through strong collaboration and leadership.

Resources Global Professionals (RGP) – Johnson & Johnson
Consultant – Project Manager

Makati City, NCR, Philippines
August 2023 – August 2024

- **Project Initiation and Finance Management:** Drove the Initiating Focus Area activities, developing project budgets and conducting Value Case Assessments aligned with the organization's strategic objectives (Project Value Creation).
- **Strategic Stakeholder Engagement:** Used Power Skills and Business Acumen to build relationships with organizational leaders, providing insights for Portfolio Management demand and aligning project outcomes with broader strategic goals.
- **Risk Mitigation & Monitoring:** Executed the Risk Performance Domain by conducting risk assessments and developing structured Contingency Plans, ensuring accurate and timely status reporting for project milestones and financial health (Monitor and Control Finances).
- **Knowledge Transfer & Closing:** Managed technical and organizational knowledge transfer, successfully transitioning deliverables, process documentation, and project outcomes into Johnson & Johnson's Global Services operations (Final Product, Service, or Result Transition).
- **Governance Contribution:** Contributed expertise to the PMO in the Governance Performance Domain, focusing on defining sustainable portfolio and project management Practices and providing coaching and direction to team members.

Automatic Data Processing (ADP) Philippines, Inc.
Project Leader

Makati City, NCR, Philippines
March 2019 – August 2023

- **Value-Driven Portfolio Execution:** Managed a High-Velocity Portfolio encompassing 180+ discrete projects, applying the Focus on Value principle to systems integration initiatives that collectively generated \$1M+ in Business Value (financial outcomes).
- **Tailored Approach Implementation:** Expertise in actively tailoring the development approach by implementing both Predictive (Waterfall) and Adaptive (Agile/Iterative) methodologies, optimizing efficiency based on specific project constraints and scope volatility.
- **Planning and Artifacts:** Oversaw the Planning Focus Area by developing comprehensive project Artifacts (plans, scope statements) that documented milestones, deliverables, and resource assignments.
- **Iterative Control and Risk Response:** Managed the Monitoring and Controlling Focus Area through iterative controls, tracking metrics, and implementing proactive Risk Response Strategies to ensure successful on-time completion of work packages.
- **Empowered Culture & PMIS:** Led teams of project managers by fostering collaboration (Build an Empowered Culture) and leveraging a Project Management Information System (PMIS) (including MS Project, ClickUp, and Siebel CRM) to integrate schedules, documentation, and reporting.

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Sterling BackCheck
Verification Specialist

Taguig City, NCR, Philippines
April 2015 - March 2019

- **Quality Assurance in Operations:** Maintained high standards of Operational Efficiency by implementing systematic control techniques (Manage Quality Assurance) to ensure data accuracy and compliance with industry regulations.
- **Process Compliance & Quality:** Performed highly specialized Perform Work functions, including comprehensive verifications (Employment, Education, Licensing), consistently ensuring that output deliverables met defined specifications and thresholds (Embed Quality principle).
- **Organizational Process Asset (OPA) Management:** Applied strong analytical capabilities and Documentation Precision to contribute and maintain the organizational knowledge repositories, ensuring process assets were accurate for future reference.
- **Stakeholder Communication:** Employed strong Communication Skills (written and verbal) for effective interaction with clients and candidates, which is foundational to the Stakeholders Performance Domain.

CERTIFICATIONS

Atlassian

Agile Project Management Professional Certificate

Makati City, NCR, Philippines
Certification Date: August 2024

Project Management Institute (PMI)
Project Management Professional (PMP)

Makati City, NCR, Philippines
Certification Date: May 2023

SAS Management Incorporated
Introduction to Agile Project Management

Makati City, NCR, Philippines
Certification Date: March 2021

ScrumStudy by VMEdu.com
Scrum Fundamentals Certified (SFC)

Las Pinas City, NCR, Philippines
Certification Date: April 2020

Project Management Institute (PMI)
Certified Associate in Project Management (CAPM)

Makati City, NCR, Philippines
Certification Date: February 2020

Elevate Six Sigma
Certified Lean Six Sigma Yellow Belt (CLSSYB)

Makati City, NCR, Philippines
Certification Date: September 2019

Professional Regulation Commission (PRC)
Registered Psychometrician (RPM)

Pasay City, NCR, Philippines
Certification Date: August 2015

EDUCATION

San Beda College Alabang (SBCA)
Master's in Business Administration (MBA)

Muntinlupa City, NCR, Philippines
Graduation Date: July 2026

San Beda College Alabang
Bachelor of Arts in Psychology (BAP)

Muntinlupa City, NCR, Philippines
Graduation Date: March 2015

VOLUNTEER EXPERIENCE

San Beda College Alabang (SBCA)
Graduate School Internal Vice-President

Muntinlupa City, NCR, Philippines
May 2025 – Present

- Led internal operations and governance for the MBA Student Council, driving strategic planning, resource coordination, and execution of academic forums and networking events to enhance graduate student engagement and collaboration with faculty and external partners.

Project Management Institute (PMI)
PMI Infinity - AI Product Tester

Las Pinas City, NCR, Philippines
January 2024 – February 2024

- Contributed to the development of PMI Infinity, an innovative AI tool designed to assist project managers in their daily tasks.

Generations Business Resource Group (BRG)
Director of Membership

Makati City, NCR, Philippines
November 2019 – October 2020

- Partnered with department managers in various business units, managed the recruitment of potential members across all tenure levels, and facilitated virtual events with 350+ attendees.

SKILLS & TECHNICAL PROFICIENCY

- **Project Management Tools:** ServiceNow, Planview, Azure DevOps, MS Project, Financial Force.
- **Agile & Workflow Automation:** Jira, ClickUp, Trello, Make.com.
- **Generative AI & Automation:** ChatGPT, Claude, Gemini, Copilot, DeepSeek.
- **Collaboration & Documentation:** MS Teams, Microsoft 365, SharePoint, OneDrive.
- **Data & Visualization Tools:** MS Excel, Miro, Gamma, Draw.io, PowerPoint, Canva.